

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D1.1 Report on use case requirements

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
3PL	third-party Logistics
4G	fourth generation network
5G	fifth generation network
5GC	5G Core
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
API	Application Programming Interface
APICS	Antwerp Port Information and Control System
AR	Augmented reality
CaaS	Container as a Service
CAN	Controller Area Network
CNF	Cloud-native Network Functions
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment
DL	Down Link
DN	Data Network
DVR	Digital Video Recorder
E2E	End to End
ECM	Evolved Packet System Connection Management
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
eMBC	Enhanced Mobile Broadband Communications
eNB	evolved Node B
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival

FEFO	First Expired, First Out
FIFO	First In, First Out
GIS	Geographic Information System
gNB	Next Generation Node B
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HD	High Definition
HDD	Hard Digital Disk
HW	Hardware
IaaS	Infrastructure as a service
ICE	Inland, Coastal & Estuary
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAN	Local Area Network
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
MANO	Management and Orchestration
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NetApp	Network Application
NFV	Network functions virtualisation
NVR	Network Video Recorder

NSA	Non-Stand Alone
NSSAI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
NST	Network Slice Template
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OBU	On-Board Units
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OSM	Open Source Management and Orchestration
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
PMR	Private Mobile Radio
PoA	Port of Antwerp
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RPM	Revolutions per Minute
SA	Stand Alone
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SCC	Shore Control Centers
SW	Software
T&L	Transport & Logistics
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
TOS	Terminal Operating System
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UL	Up Link
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications
USB	Universal Serial Bus

VA	Vertical-Agnostic NetApp
vCPU	virtual Central Processing Unit
vEPC	virtual Evolved Packet Core
VHF	Very High Frequency
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
VS	Vertical-Specific NetApp
Vsat	Very small aperture terminal
WMS	Warehouse Management System

Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.1 “Report on use case requirements” is one of WP1 “Use Cases, Requirements Analysis and Architecture” reports. It includes the outcomes of T1.1 “Use case requirements and analysis”. T1.1 focuses on the identification of the T&L sector requirements, which should be mapped to VITAL-5G Use Cases. There are three Use Cases which are designed in three experimentation areas:

- Use case 1: Automated vessel transport, which will be tested in Port of Antwerp
- Use case 2: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras, which will be tested in Danube River
- Use case 3: Automation and remote operation of freight logistics, which will be tested in Athens logistics hub

D1.1 provides a high-level description of the VITAL-5G use cases and identifies the main requirements of these use cases. The requirements, which are separated into business, application and network requirements, will be the basis on which the design and implementation of facilities subsystems will take place.

Based on the requirements analysis performed in this deliverable, an early, high-level, approach regarding the NetApp(s) functionality that will be developed for each use case is presented. Additionally, early insights on the required VITAL-5G platform requirements, based on the targeted supported functionality for the use cases, are provided. The full NetApp design and VITAL-5G platform requirements and design, will be presented in the following WP1 deliverables.

1 Introduction

VITAL-5G focuses on the design and implementation of a flexible facility that could host network applications which will optimize the performance and the output of the Transport & Logistics vertical sector. For that purpose, 13 Network Applications (NetApps) will be developed so as to address specific industry challenges. In order to showcase the advantages of VITAL-5G solution, three Use Cases are designed in three experimentation areas:

- Use case 1: Automated vessel transport, which will be tested in Port of Antwerp
- Use case 2: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras, which will be tested in Danube River
- Use case 3: Automation and remote operation of freight logistics, which will be tested in Athens logistics hub

This document provides a description of the Use Cases, as well as the Site facilities. Additionally, the requirements of each use case are identified and analysed. These requirements are categorized into three groups: Business, Application and Network requirements.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T1.1 Use case requirements and analysis	This task will identify the main requirements of the T&L sector by taking contributions from previous projects, standards bodies and VITAL-5G vertical industries partners.	Chapter 3	In Chapter 3 there is a general description of the requirements.
	This task will first focus on the requirements definition and analysis by project vertical industries partners, starting with the analysis of the use cases. Each T&L stakeholder will identify the high-level use case requirements which in turn will be translated into VITAL-5G	Chapter 2 Chapter 3	The Use Cases are described in chapter 2. Information about related service Key Performance Indicators and the NetApps that will be used is also provided. Then in Chapter 3 the high-level use case requirements are presented.

	experimentation facility requirements.		
	These requirements will be mapped to the usage scenarios, technical requirements, and technologies in 5G networks needed to efficiently support convincing trials in the T&L sector.	Chapter 3	The requirements are categorised into business, application and network and are mapped to each use case in Chapter 3.
	The use case requirements will also act as a driver for the necessary supported functionality from the VITAL-5G platform and open repository	Chapter 4	In Chapter 4 a description of the VITAL-5G platform is presented as well as the Platform requirements, identified from the analysis of the three VITAL-5G use cases.
DELIVERABLE			
D1.1 Report on use case requirements			
Report containing the requirements analysis results of the internal VITAL-5G use cases and their detailed definition.			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

One of the primary goals of this report is to describe in detail the VITAL-5G use cases, along with their requirements. More specifically, Section 2 provides the description of the three use cases of the project, namely:

- Use case 1: Automated vessel transport
- Use case 2: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras
- Use case 3: Automation and remote operation of freight logistics

Apart from the general description of the use cases, information about service Key Performance Indicators and the NetApps that will be used in each use case is provided. Additionally, the scenarios that will be tested are described in Section 2, as well as the facilities where the scenarios will be implemented.

Section 3 focuses on the requirements' analysis. The requirements are separated into three categories:

- Business requirements, which includes the key performance indicators related to indoor and inland logistics
- Application requirements, which are requirements of the Hardware (HW) and Software (SW) that will be deployed
- Network requirements, which are the characteristics that the network should offer in order to support the requested applications

First, a general description of each category of requirements is provided and then the way these requirements are formulated in each use case is presented. Finally, a general description and conclusions are provided, regarding the the previous analysis of requirements.

Use Cases requirements will be used in order to identify the platform requirements. The way the requirements will affect the platform requirements is described in Section 4.

Section 5 is the final conclusion section.

2 VITAL-5G Use Cases

Section 2 presents the overview of the three VITAL-5G Use Cases (UC). It provides information about the services KPIs and the NetApps that will be used in each UC, as well as the description of the site facilities.

2.1 Use case 1: Automated Vessel Transport

2.1.1 Use Case Description

This use case deals with the application of 5G technology in a smart port context. It will be performed using a vessel provided by Seafar at the Port of Antwerp (PoA). The main goal is to showcase the automation of vessel-based logistics transport leveraging the modern 5G communications technology. This vessel will be running in a normal operational schedule, but for this use case, it will also be outfitted with additional 5G connectivity which will support high-bandwidth (preferably full HD) camera feeds, real-time sensor data coming from the vessels to the command centre, and real-time steering commands to the remote vessel. We aim to build up a real-time digital twin around the vessel to support the remotely controlled (and later on autonomous) vessels. In parallel, real-time route planning will be foreseen to optimize the port operations and to avoid idle times, based on berthing time slots provided by the port authorities and terminal operators, while the optimisation will be performed based on Machine Learning/ Artificial Intelligence (ML/AI) methodologies. The applications developed in this use-case, make use of the following types of data: vessels' location, schedule, perception data including camera streams, LiDAR point cloud, and slot data to calculate the optimal navigation speed that needs to be held by vessels to meet their slot at terminals/locks etc.

Figure 1: Vital5G Antwerp Trial Site

The goal of this use case is to address the following three main targets:

- 1) Remotely controlled and autonomous navigation: remote control and (semi-)autonomous navigation will reduce the number of on-board personnel, allowing one operator to remotely control more than one vessel (NetApps VS5 and VS6, combined with VS8, and assisted by VS7 and VA4 to select and foresee the best paths in the dock to minimize berthing time).
- 2) Navigation speed optimisation: schedules and speeds are built based on past, current and future status of port assets, avoiding vessels to unnecessarily wait while berths are in contention (NetApp VS7).
- 3) Real-time port control: simulating a Digital Twin of the port to assist in real-time port control and to foresee short-term future port status (NetApp VA4, combined with VS8).

The main stakeholders that are involved in UC#1 are:

- **Digitrans:** DigiTrans is SME and a spin-off of University of Antwerp and imec. DigiTrans develops a uniform middleware layer for integrating and processing data from various transport and logistics processes.
- **IMEC:** Research partner involved in the development of NetApps and research work over AI / ML based computer vision and path planning algorithms. IMEC is also involved in the integration of 5G network in the use case and the orchestration of the different NetApp functions.
- **Seafar NV:** Provides the vessel (Tercofin II), plus remote controllability and autonomy of this vessel.
- **Telenet:** Telenet will provide 5G connectivity, including 5G UE and a fully standalone 5G network and has a similar blueprint comparable with Telenet's 5G commercial roadmap.

2.1.2 Related service Key Performance Indicators

Antwerp is strategically located near the second largest port of Europe and therefore this UC holds importance in having a strong impact on the logistics industry in Flanders. The use case aims to have a functional plug-and-play solution to any Autonomous/remote vessel navigation system. The general business KPIs identified for this use case include:

1) (Improve) Infrastructure Safety (On shore / in waterway)

Current way of measurement is via the online Seafar Portal¹. All incidents or events are manually or automatically logged on the portal. Specific sheets can be downloaded for an overview over time.

The infrastructure safety (on shore / in waterway) should be improved by 10 to 30%.

2) Reduced dwell time in the port area

Inland navigation vessels are currently spending significant time in waiting at terminals for start the loading/unloading operations or when interrupted. This waiting time adds up to the total dwell time. Current way of measurement is via the online Seafar Portal. Navigation time and dwell time are manually or automatically logged on the portal. Specific sheets can be downloaded for an overview.

The expected reduction of dwell time in the port area ranges from 20 to 40%.

3) (Improve) vessel captain and ship planning gaps

The planning operations of inland navigation vessels at terminals inside the port are complex and planners consider a wide set of variables (the dock and lock planning, the schedule of other inland navigation vessels etc.) to complete them. Current way of planning is via the online Seafar Portal. Planning is added on the portal by inland navigation planners and captains.

Manual planning is expected to decrease by 25 to 50%.

2.1.3 Use Case 1 NetApps Description

Figure 2 shows the preliminary NetApp architecture designed for this use case.

¹ <https://portal.seafar.eu/> (regulated access)

Figure 2: NetApp architecture of the Antwerp Trial Site

Five main NetApps are envisioned as part of this use case to achieve these goals, they are presented below:

2.1.3.1 Vertical Agnostic NetApps

VA4 - Real-time Digital Twin

A real-time digital twin will be built up to construct a local copy of a situational awareness model. It makes use of all available sensor and camera data to build a real-time model of the environment. Deep Learning based distributed sensor fusion will be employed for shared situational awareness. Distributed perception extends the perceptive range of the agent (inland vessel) (currently limited to camera and sensors installed on the agent) by making use of cameras and sensors on other agents for example: water-side units. In situational awareness applications, the agent must be fully attentive. This demands a high level of perception to precisely map the environment, a task that in many cases is beyond the capabilities of the local sensors deployed on the agent, because of the blind spots that may arise due to limitations of the sensor's field of view. Consequently, there is an increased interest in distributed joint perception for situational awareness applications, as it can benefit from broadcast perception messages captured by other sensors deployed on surrounding agents.

As a result, multiple research works have been done in agent-to-agent communication to achieve distributed joint perception for shared situational awareness. The goal of distributed joint perception is to increase the perception field of view and act as a backup plan in case of local sensor failures. Besides, it increases the confidence of predictions made based on a single agent's sensors, and it also helps eliminate the blind spot regions. Also, by intelligently aggregating information received from multiple agents, the agent becomes capable of seeing through occlusions, and detect actors at longer ranges, where the observations using local sensors are very sparse or non-existent. It also enables the agent to observe the same scene from different viewpoints that will improve the perceived environment's certainty and robustness. All of that would not have been possible only with the local perception modalities.

The goal of this NetApp is to provide an extended perceptive range to the remote teleoperator for making the appropriate decisions. A system of connected sensors on a distinct and diverse range of vehicles each with their limited field of view will be foreseen. The information gathered from these diverse sensors will be aggregated and fused into a shared world model (map) which will be used by the intelligent agent for better decision making.

Data exchange between the various transport & logistics (T&L) services will be decentralized using 5G technology. The shared data from other/surrounding agents is expected to be transmitted to the agent or a cloud service managed by the stakeholders where further fusion and post-processing of this data will take place. The resulting "map" can be used by the logistics stakeholders as well as SMEs to enhance the awareness of the environment perceived by their automated/teleoperated agent. As already mentioned in the above description

of NetApps for this use case, the use of 5G connectivity will be needed to ensure the reliability of the connection (for minimum dropouts), low latency (for real timeliness), and higher bandwidth (for large amounts of data e.g.: video and point cloud streams).

Shared situational awareness is a major challenge facing intelligent transport systems and will be used to validate and verify the T&L related cutting-edge NetApps. Below is an example of a potential use case that can be used to showcase the added value of 5G connectivity (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Digital Twin

Example: Perception and AIS data shared between vessels to detect near and far objects to create a map of the obstacles ahead. Sharing data with sea/river port authorities or teleoperators to inspect the situation in real-time and take proper actions. Data can be shared to the cloud computing centre for data processing and fusion.

As with NetApp VS7, VA4 will not require specific 5G network requirements, although it could leverage from mMTC, to enable device-to-device communication between the Digital Twin and the sensors in the vessel. Additionally, the functions contained in this NetApp need to be able to be deployed and instantiated by the network orchestrator.

2.1.3.2 Vertical Specific NetApps

VS5 - Remote Vessel Navigation:

Remote navigation system of the vessel (manual control), making use of a waypoint command interface and the data utility service for serving the streams of received sensor data from the vessel to the control center. It also includes monitoring of sensor data, obstacle detection and tracking, path prediction, etc.

Seafar NV is an independent ship management company that develops technology to remotely operate automated vessels for ICE (Inland, Coastal & Estuary) shipping. The economic motivation is straightforward: Seafar wishes to market technology solutions and associated services to facilitate remote controlled and autonomous navigation for its clients who are ICE ship operators.

At this moment, Seafar already operates a remotely operated vessel fleet in Flanders and the Netherlands. To establish a connection between the vessels and the Shore Control Centre's teleoperation software, the company currently solely relies on the existing 4G infrastructure. Reliable communication is of utmost importance for

remote or autonomous navigation. By seamlessly combining different wireless technologies (4G, VSAT, WiFi etc.), Seafar aims to obtain the most reliable connection possible. Within this NetApp, 5G will be incorporated in this set of connections to enhance the connection's quality.

Using 5G, Seafar will be able to obtain a lot more information at any given time about the vessel's surroundings. With 4G, they are limited to about 3 High Definition (HD) video streams and some lower resolution streams. 5G should open the path to quicker, lower latency connections providing us with more (full) HD video streams, and better response times.

Remote vessel navigation will be performed completely by the vessel operator in the Shore Control Center, with the support of onboard crew. Vessels are operated from the control center by licensed captains with a long track record in inland and maritime navigation.

In order to provide the vessels with the 5G connectivity, in this NetApp will make use of carefully deployed small / large 5G cells in different pilot areas. This will ensure that the connectivity in the vessels has the required reliability, performing seamless handovers in the vessels' transit through the port. Connectivity will be provided through network slices, and network slicing templates will be used to specify the per-service requirements. The 5G scenarios foreseen for this NetApp are Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC) to ensure the required low latency between the vessel and the control center. In addition, an orchestration platform for container-based deployment will be used to facilitate Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement towards achieving end-to-end low latency in the different NetApp sub-tasks.

VS6 - Autonomous Vessel Navigation Control:

Autonomous navigation control system of the vessel, making use of a digital twin (i.e., VA4) of the vessel and including monitoring of sensor data, obstacle detection and tracking, path prediction, etc.

Seafar and IMEC share a long-term goal of bringing autonomy to the inland vessels. For this task, they coordinate together in bringing real time data aggregation for navigation planning. Another major point, where IMEC supports Seafar is with environmental perception which is of utmost importance for building autonomous control to the vessels, it includes obstacle detection and avoidance in the inland waterways.

In this NetApp, IDLab works to allow ships to sail autonomously through the inland waterways of Flanders. To achieve this goal, we focus on two different aspects of autonomous sailing. First, we need to be able to detect and localize objects around the ship. We will use both RGB cameras and LiDAR sensors to get an accurate view of all obstacles around the ship. Secondly, we use this information to calculate a course for the ship to sail. We do this by applying state-of-the-art reinforcement learning (RL) techniques.

Figure 4: Object detection on RGB camera data

To enable autonomous vessels to operate on inland waterways, they need to detect, track and localize objects in the near distance to safely navigate. We will deploy current deep learning techniques (YOLOv3 with DeepSORT [1]) to detect and track these objects (see Figure 4). In general, deep learning requires a large amount of labelled data, however, by using pre-existing similar datasets, we were able to significantly decrease the needed amount of labelled data from the target distribution. We plan to achieve a mean Average Precision of above 80 % on the boat class. Our second goal is to estimate the relative distance of the objects based on the generated bounding boxes. All these methods can run in real-time on the vessel with a fps of 1.83 on a 2.7GHz vCPU.

Figure 5: Map (left) and binarization (right) of a section of the Schelde river in Antwerp

In reinforcement learning it is important to have a good simulation environment to train the agents. We created a shipping simulation environment to use during the development of this NetApp. In this environment we can simulate a ship sailing through a waterway. We can include any waterway desired by importing it as a binary image into the simulation (see Figure 5). As observation, the agent receives a portion of the binary map around its current location, the distance to its goal and the relative heading to its goal. This provides the agent with enough information to sail autonomously. As an action, the agent can choose a heading and speed for the ship to maintain. Afterwards the agent is rewarded based on the distance to the goal and any possible collisions. Currently, we are using proximal policy optimisation (PPO), a state-of-the-art RL methodology to train the agents. By using these techniques, we will be able to allow a ship to safely navigate in simulation environments.

Just like VS5, the VS6 NetApp will use the Telenet 5G deployment to meet the required connection reliability. As in VS5, always on connectivity will be provided through network slices, which will be configured through network slicing templates. It will require URLLC to satisfy a low latency between the vessel and the digital twin and eMBB to guarantee a large enough bandwidth to transmit videos the high-definition quality to the control centre, where AI-based algorithms may be deployed to offload computation from the Vessel.

Additionally, this NetApp will perform proactive latency-aware VNF / container placement/relocation to ensure that the different AI-based data processing systems provide timely responses to the vessels when required. This placement will be based on real-time data input monitored from the actual network KPIs measured in the 5G network. Some of these VNFs will be Deep learning-based computer vision models for dynamic obstacle avoidance in inland waterways. They may be deployed in the Vessel or in the control centre depending on the computational and latency requirements.

VS7 - Navigation Speed Optimizer:

DigiTrans develops the Navigation Speed Optimizer as tool to help vessel operators in daily navigation tasks. Currently the vessel operators are sailing considering a pre-determined planning that is based on origin and destination data. Regarding navigation speed, vessel operators usually give preference to sail at the maximum allowed navigation speed. The consequence of sailing at the maximum speed is that vessels are burning more fuel and arrive at sub-optimal moments at their destination, namely at a timing earlier than the available time-window to be operated (loaded or unloaded), so they need to wait. The Navigation Speed Optimizer developed by DigiTrans connects to multiple sources of data and indicates the optimal speed that need to be hold so that the vessels arrive just in time at its destination (with a speed that allows lower fuel consumption and without having to wait before being loaded or unloaded). DigiTrans positions itself as a data integrator for the transport and logistics sector and has spent the past two years intensively researching the Belgian logistics market. DigiTrans develops the Navigation Speed Optimizer so that its users can work more efficiently. It does so by bringing real-time data from different systems and process it in the 5G framework to provide real-time optimal navigation indication, such as the optimal navigation speed. This is a niche that DigiTrans tries to fill.

Figure 6 displays how the Navigation Speed Optimizer is solved in current operations and the set-up where the Navigation Speed Optimizer NetApp functions.

Figure 6: Set-up where Navigation Speed Optimizer works

The Navigation Speed Optimizer makes use of the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), schedule, and slot data to calculate the optimal navigation speed (v_{optimal}) that needs to be held by vessels to meet their appointment at the final (e.g., terminal quay side in ports) or intermediary check points (e.g., appointments at locks). It retrieves real-time data with regard to navigation and idling parameters and processes it. It requires input from the applications that make use of 5G network capabilities to improve data quality regarding vessel position, locks usage etc. It provides the optimal vessel speed to the (semi-)autonomous navigation dashboard and algorithms that remotely control vessels' speed.

The principle of the Navigation Speed Optimizer is sketched on Figure 7.

Figure 7: The use of optimal navigation speed to arrive just in time at the destination at expected time window slots

Figure 8 shows which data is retrieved to calculate the optimal navigation speed. The examples given regarding data sources are set from the perspective of implementing the Navigation Speed Optimizer at vessels which call at the Port of Antwerp.

Figure 8: Type of data sources to be integrated in the Navigation Speed Optimizer app

The main characteristics of this NetApp are:

- Development of a universal data integration framework to connect and handle data streaming from multiple sources (port lock planning e.g., Antwerp Port Information and Control System (APICS), terminal waterside planning, terminal operating system (TOS), and historical data sources regarding sailing or lock passage).
- Opens up an Application Programming Interface (API) that allows retrieving the optimal navigation speed for vessel operators who need it.
- Deploy the speed optimizer algorithm in the production environment.

This NetApp will not require specific 5G network requirements. However, the functions contained in this NetApp will be able to be deployed and instantiated by the network orchestrator.

VS8 - On-board data collection & interfacing for vessels:

Collect data from on board sensors (water speed, water depth, outside/inside temperature, engine functional parameters, etc.) and from video cameras placed on board of the ship. All data are made available for the local on-board server and providing the interface to/from external nodes and the 5G network. This software application will be developed at the level of a server that has specific interfaces for different types of on board installed devices and surveillance modules. The data is formatted in a way that it can be understood and treated by the next level NetApp. The main characteristics of this NetApp are:

- Kubernetes-based orchestration tool and algorithms for container placement. These containers will contain the software required to interact with the sensors and actuators in the vessels.
- Management and orchestration of heterogeneous nodes (with deployed VNFs) within the vessel infrastructure with a real-time monitoring input.

The 5G scenario foreseen for this NetApp are URLLC to ensure the required low latency for the data transmitted from the vessel to the control centre, and vice versa.

Seafar vessels include a standard set of sensors whose data will be accessible by the server. The most important ones for this UC include the following:

a. Cameras

Figure 9: IP cameras

The vessel is outfitted with a number of IP cameras (i.e., Figure 9), providing a H.264 stream. Using an RSTP URL, one can easily obtain a camera's image. The brand of cameras is Axis, a world leader in outdoor controllable cameras.

b. Location

A Hemisphere Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) installation is available for the usual latitude/longitude values, but also the heading, pitch, speed, altitude can be accessed on this device.

c. Engine parameters

Figure 10: Programmable Logic Controller

Using a Controller Area Network (CAN) bus interface, the engines' parameters become visible such as Revolutions per Minute (RPM), Oil level, Temperature, Torque, etc.

2.1.4 Site Facilities Description

2.1.4.1 Trial facility

The implementation of the NetApps will be demonstrated on an example real-case scenario using the Antwerp testbed area presented in Figure 11. The ship will navigate from a starting point A to a destination point B, with autonomous navigation (VS6) for part of the route that goes over the Scheldt River (yellow arrow) and remote control navigation (VS5) for part in the channel that ends in point B (blue arrow). The other NetApps (VS7, VS8 and VA4) assist the operation of VS5 and will also be demonstrated.

Figure 11: Map of the UC#1 testbed area in Antwerp

2.1.4.2 Trial HW & SW

Teleoperation site: Seafar has 3 so-called Shore Control Centres (SCC). The one in Antwerp will be used for teleoperation of the vessel (see Figure 12). In each SCC, there are several Shore Control Station, which are basically large format desks with a 6-screen video-wall in front of them. On the desk joysticks were mounted, other screens with navigational information, emergency stops, communication devices, etc. The control centre part of the NetApps will be deployed in the Teleoperation site.

Figure 12: Teleoperation Centre at Seafar Antwerp Office

Vessel: Seafar will demonstrate the functionality of the different NetApps with Tercofin II (see Figure 13). This is an inland container vessel which usually sails between Port of Antwerp and Liege.

Figure 13: Tercofin II vessel owned by Seafar

2.1.4.3 Targeted trial scenarios

The targeted trial scenarios to be demonstrated in the Port of Antwerp, correspond to the Vertical Specific (VS) NetApp functionalities described in Section 2.1.3.2. A more detailed scenario description will be provided in the follow up deliverables, as the architecture/design of the various NetApps (and hence their capabilities/functionality) are finalized.

2.2 Use case 2: 5G Connectivity and Data-Enabled Assisted Navigation Using IoT Sensing and Video Cameras

2.2.1 Use case Description

The objective of Use Case 2 is focused on the implementation of a data-enabled assisted navigation application using Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensing system and video cameras installed in Galati port and on ships and barges (cargos). The Galati port is an entry point for large shipping traffic from the Black Sea towards continental Europe and is part of the Rhine-Danube Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) Corridor². It is the largest port on the Danube River and the second largest Romanian port.

The UC application proposed will permit a safer port operation and more security regarding navigation of ships with the help of assisted operation / navigation even in severe weather and water conditions.

The Romanian test case study will be performed on a series of ships belonging to CNFR NAVROM. NAVROM is a Romanian river transport company, carrying millions of tons of various goods through both internal (Galati, Constanta etc.) and external routes to Ukraine, Bulgaria, Austria, Germany etc. It has a tradition of over 100 years, being an important European inland shipowner.

In the activity of operating the ships, it is necessary to implement technologies for communication and monitoring of voyages, as a source for correcting the weak points. Thus, to avoid stationary downtime due to navigation errors, and to respectively reduce as much as possible the transport of empty units, while achieving a higher percentage of loading, it is required better communication between ships and dispatchers as well as between ships and ports of operation. This can be achieved by a real-time connectivity of the radio and video

² https://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/infrastructure/ten-t_en

navigation equipment of the sensors that monitor the operating parameters of the ship with the dispatcher office and / or the safety of the navigation department. Also, for better sailing safety, a connection between the decision departments (the Fleet operation department) and ships is necessary for getting out of difficult situations.

All sensors and cameras will enable the interoperable wireless protocols over a private 5G network and will permit the extension of Internet connectivity of the sensing system. Several sensors, that will be described in this section, such as GPS, humidity, smoke, engine power sensors located in the machine room, will be installed on the ship and barges. These sensors provide relevant information such as velocity, heading, water and wind speed, etc. to the ship local monitoring equipment, allowing the captain and crew to take proper decisions and supporting on-board diagnosis. The crew will also have access to live video streaming from the surroundings through high-definition video cameras in order to achieve high-resolution video streams, high connectivity and low latency that is uniquely offered by 5G.

The Galati port 5G testbed will be based on existing Orange 5G facility built with components from ICT-17's 5G-EVE project³; it will be upgraded with additional 3GPP Rel.16⁴ features and extended to provide coverage at the Galati port.

Use case 2 targets the following achievements:

- Reduced number of dangerous navigation events occurrences (vessel collisions, ships stuck in the river because of sandbanks or shallow waters etc.) by collecting and transmitting the sensors and video data through Data Stream Organisation NetApp VA5.
- Reduced logistic costs due to proper decisions based on on-board diagnosis and monitoring functions, therefore limiting the impact of the human factor to take potentially wrong decisions. This can be achieved through On-board data collection & interfacing for vessels NetApp VS8.
- A more accurate electronic navigation map using Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing NetApp VA1.

As an extension to this use case, INCE proposes the use of a set of sensors and the analysis of the corresponding data streams based on AI/ML mechanisms which can provide a significantly enhanced level of assurance about the vessels' cargo integrity (to ensure that the cargo has remained intact during all the way from the origin to the destination) compared to the current use of special seals that actually tries to secure only the door of the container. Measured parameters could include the oxygen level in the container, the light intensity or the humidity. Data fusion and post-processing could reveal potential cargo tampering. The information of such sensors could also be used for checking the air quality before the workers open the container, which is important for their safety, as many times due to the nature of the cargo and the long transport duration, dangerous gasses and other life-threatening conditions are created. From 5G network point of view, there is no additional or different requirement to support this use case extension compared to the network requirements for the main purpose of the use case.

The main stakeholders that are involved in UC#2 are:

- NAVROM, which is a Romanian river transport company and will offer services in the T&L sector
- BEIA, which is the administrator of the VITAL5G Platform and offers experimentation as a service, consultancy and NetApp repository marketplace

³ Through ICT-17 projects, 5G infrastructures become available to verticals to test their applications. 5G-EVE is the 5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials, the project that creates the foundations for a pervasive roll-out of end-to-end 5G networks in Europe by offering to vertical industries and to all 5G-PPP Phase3 projects facilities to validate their network KPIs and their services. ICT-17's 5G-EVE project testbed is based on OpenAir Interface over virtualized infrastructure (K8s) for RAN & Core, fully virtualized and automated network deployment, 5G NSA RAN and Core 3GPP Rel 15.

⁴ 3GPP Release 16 is a major release for 5G, the second and evolved set of 5G standards, often referred to as "5G phase 2". <https://www.3gpp.org/release-16>

- ORO, whose network is used to provide 5G network
- ATG, which is a T&L Vertical Stakeholders

2.2.2 Related Service Key Performance Indicators

Due to the difficult existing navigation conditions the rate of incidents involving vessels increased involving high costs of repairing the damages and for human resources. Safety systems for general navigation are the basic tools to fix vessel position, obtain information about the physical environment and operating conditions, and communicate with other vessels and shore-based personnel. These systems should include a database used for safety-related policymaking and decision-making that includes the global positioning system (GPS) and other navigational aids, hydrographic data, nautical charts, port-specific and general information about waterways, and data on tides and currents. The technology will improve the operations, safety and waterways management system, helping the: crews who are responsible for handling the vessel and who know its capabilities and limitations; the system operators who provide navigation information to vessels; the pilots, who need accurate and timely information; the ground personnel, who must make decisions based on the conditions and other traffic in the area.

NAVROM will participate in the VITAL-5G platform as the beneficiary of the project results. A series of equipment provided by BEIA will be installed on a series of ships within the company from which a series of data and useful information in the project will be collected for NetApps verification and validation.

The data collected from the ships are useful and will improve the management of the daily activity. Many savings are expected to be achieved, especially in fuel consumption and in reducing travel time. Reaching the goods to the destination is a beneficial thing for the contract partners, especially in a competitive market.

The main Business/services KPIs targeted in this use case are the following:

- **Decrease in logistic cost by 15%**
 - Way of measurement: Logistics costs may include service, transportation, inventory and warehouse costs. The partners will measure the logistics costs with and without taking into account On-Board Diagnostics (OBD) assisted decisions, by comparing the costs reported by the NAVROM port operator for different periods of time, i.e., percentage of human resources reduction (personnel / crew).
 - Baseline: NAVROM port operator has 200 people as navigating personnel serving the ships.
 - Means of achieving KPI: By using the on board data collection & interfacing for vessels NetApp VS8, the maintenance cost will be reduced due to proper decisions based on on-board diagnosis and monitoring functions and, thus will limit the impact of the human factor to take potentially wrong decisions.
- **Decrease in dangerous navigation events occurrences by 20%**
 - Way of measurement: Decrease of dangerous navigation events, e.g., vessel collisions, tows striking bridges, ships or barges stuck in the river due to sandbanks or shallow water depth, difficulties, under typical waterway conditions (storms, high water and flood events) The partners will collect the classified events by the NetApp and measure the decrease against the Romanian database of navigation events.
 - Baseline: The average number of dangerous events/issues occurred on the Danube river is currently in the order of five events per year.
 - Means of achieving KPI: By using the Data stream organisation NetApp VA5, each event will be rapidly, distinctly and granularly classified into dangerous/non-dangerous as well as the type of dangerous event. Warnings will be immediately issued leading to improved reaction time from the vessel crew.
- **Increase in accuracy of electronic navigation maps creation by 20%**
 - Way of measurement: The accuracy of electronic navigation maps indicates vessel course, distance and bearing line from a vessel or in between external objects. The accuracy of

- positioning due to Geographic Information System (GIS) software is used together with several information layers, e.g., bathymetric maps, map showing recommended routes and showing safe depth limits, obstacles or dangerous places, thus improving the safety navigation.
- Baseline: Electronic maps used in the navigation process offer currently an accuracy of about 20-35 m (composed of positional accuracy of charted seabed feature 15-20 m and GNSS accuracy 5- 15m⁶).
 - Means of achieving Key Performance Indicators (KPI): The correct safe distance for a ship is made of positional accuracy of charted seabed feature, half ship's beam, GNSS accuracy and ship orientation / motion. The accuracy of positioning due to GNSS can be improved by the use of distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing NetApp VA1, which will use data from sensors such as: velocity, heading, water and wind speed, etc. as well as video stream data. Fusion of GNSS data with sensor data may lead to a total 10% in accuracy of electronic navigation maps.

2.2.3 Use Case 2 NetApps description

Three NetApps will be developed for the “5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras” use case, implemented in the Romanian partners premises. Two of the NetApps are vertical agnostic and target the delivery of generic functionalities that can be reused within the port or any other logistics environment, while the third one will deliver specific vertical functionalities targeting the port environment of RO trial site. The detailed description of the NetApps to be developed as part of this use case are provided below

2.2.3.1 Vertical Agnostic NetApps

VA1 - Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing:

Data ingestion, fusion and post-processing functionality from distributed data sources; Cloud based decisions from resulting analytics; issuing of warning, notifications, reporting. Existing AI / Data analytics tools and inspection application will be used as a starting point, and they will be enhanced with additional fusion, and analytics functionality, and transformed to NetApps. The VA1 is described in more detail in UC#3 (see Section 2.3.3.1). We would like to point out, however, that for UC#2 it *will support the targeted improvement in accuracy of electronic navigation maps creation.*

VA1 Inputs:

- sensor data in different formats

VA1 Outputs:

- fused data
- data analytics
- decisions
- warnings
- notifications
- reports

VA5 - Data stream organisation:

Organizing data streams to be transmitted to the navigation centre using 5G network parameters in a very efficient way. Video streaming and data coming from different sensors (GPS, humidity, smoke, velocity, etc.) are transmitted to the navigation centre using wireless protocols over a private 5G network and permit the extension of the Internet connectivity of the sensing system to be used by specific applications, e.g., assisted navigation for avoiding collisions, diagnosis, etc. For UC#2, it will support the targeted improvement in navigation dangerous events occurrences related issues. Figure 14 presents a high-level description of VA5.

VA5 can be illustrated in a hierarchical manner, using a layer-based approach, however we foresee some cross-layer components. The communication between all these layers is enabled by a data bus that crosses all the different domains.

- Physical layer represents the actual data coming from sensors as well as video streams. This layer is made of all the different sensors, devices and client agents that are in charge of collecting and transmitting data to the NetApp. Due to the different nature of the sensors as well as the different UC sites, this layer is likely to be very heterogeneous in terms of technologies, networks, protocols. In order to standardize the process of context data integration VA5 will adhere to a common data model.
- NetApp middleware layer offers relevant enablers for each UC needs, from device integration to complex event processing. The main component of the middleware is the data ingestion and integration block, which links the physical layer with the output layer using a data bus.
- NetApp core layer is in charge of transforming plain data into knowledge to enrich the higher-level decision support services with intelligence.
- NetApp exploitation/output layer is on top of the core layer and fed by it through what is called the Decision support mediator. The mediator provides data and content to enable the VA5 outputs for UC stakeholders.
- VITAL-5G applications (not in scope of NetApp definition) will build on the NetApp outputs to enable users to interact with the VITAL-5G platform
- Security components will span all layers and facilitate the efficient and secure communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure.

Figure 14: High-level description of VA5

VA5 Inputs:

- Video stream in WebRTC format
- Sensor data in JSON payload over MQTT

VA5 Outputs (provisional):

- decision support
- collision avoidance assisted navigation

- diagnosis
- river parameters (water depth, temperature, velocity, different obstacles) and weather conditions

2.2.3.2 Vertical Specific NetApps

VS8 - On board data collection & interfacing for vessels:

Collect data from on board sensors (water speed, water depth, outside/inside temperature, engine functional parameters, etc.) and from video cameras placed on board of the ship. All data is made available for the local on-board server and provides the interface to/from external edge nodes and the 5G network. This software application will be developed at the level of a server that has specific interfaces for different types of on board installed devices and surveillance modules. The data is formatted in a way to be understood and treated by the next level NetApp. For UC#2, it will support the targeted cost reduction. A high-level description of VS8 is provided in Figure 15.

Figure 15: VS8 data sources and functional components (provisional)

VS8 Inputs:

- ship sensors
 - water speed,
 - water depth,
 - outside/inside temperature,
 - engine functional parameters
- ship video stream

VS8 Outputs:

- API endpoints towards edge nodes and 5G network
- API endpoints towards other NetApps

2.2.4 Site facilities & trial scenarios description

2.2.4.1 Trial facility

The facility is architecturally composed of 5G network components that will evolve during the life cycle of the project to an End-to-End (E2E) 5G infrastructure, able to cope with the projects NetApps needs.

Figure 16: 5G Orange Lab in Bucharest

The main integration and development activities will take place in Orange Bucharest 5G LAB (Figure 16), following several phases of implementation and later the same service infrastructure will be extended to Galati.

Figure 17: ORO Bucharest 5G facility

The Romanian facility deployment, depicted schematically in Figure 17, consists of three main implementation and validation steps:

Phase 1: 5G NSA testbed, Bucharest composed by 5G NSA Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core (vEPC & 5G RAN network integration), 5G NSA Option 3x. 5G-EVE/5G-VICTORI ICT-17/19 5G testbed (Figure 18) based on OpenAirInterface over virtualized infrastructure (K8s) for RAN & Core, fully virtualized and automated network deployment, 5G NSA/SA RAN and Core 3GPP Rel. 15.

Figure 18: The 5G ICT-17/19 platform

Phase 2: 5G private standalone network, PMR, that is integrated with the Bucharest testbed and is 3GPP Release 16, running on dedicated virtualized infrastructure, 5G SA option 2 implementations as seen in Figure 19.

Figure 19: 5G PMR Rel. 16 architecture on virtualized infrastructure

The 5G PMR provides 5G Standalone (SA) connectivity, service network slice implementation for the Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB)/URLLC use case’s communication needs. The PMR is communicating through the DN with the NetApps Cloud infrastructure in Bucharest testbed within the required KPIs in terms of bandwidth and latency.

Phase 3: 5G SA, the 5G system mainly based on a virtualized network, also including some physical network components implemented by the 5G Service Based Architecture., 5G SA RAN and Core, Option 2, 3GPP Release 16.

Galati 5G site specifically designed for this use case will be installed and integrated by ORO in H2 2021 in NSA configuration and will consist in two 5G sectors that will cover NAVROM ships positions and headquarter, as presented in Figure 39. Facility planning is depicted in Figure 20.

Figure 20: ORO facility planning

2.2.4.2 Trial HW & SW

Figure 21: Ship components diagram

Figure 21 depicts the ship components diagram. The following components on the ship will be used:

- hardware:
 - AIS transponder (SAAB R4 or Periskal PM-1)
 - HIKVISION DVR and video cameras
 - ACTISENSE DST 2 converter
 - PLC (Siemens IoT 20xx or Raspberry PI)
 - CAN-BUS interface for Caterpillar (Diesel Mecanica Constanta)
- sensors:
 - Depth sensor type Airmar SS505

The positioning of hardware and sensors is presented in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Positioning of hardware and sensors on a ship

The Automatic Identification System (AIS) TRANSPONDER is an equipment that provides data about the type of ship, the position of the ship, the speed of the ship, the angle made by the North direction, the type of voyage to be made, the estimated time to the end that trip, etc. It is based on the information received from a GPS antenna and very high frequency (VHF) radio connection with the radio relays installed along the Danube installed in this system. All data are processed and retransmitted to ships from the web server installed (for the Romanian sector) in Constanta. The same types of relays and web servers are in the other countries bordering

the Danube (Bulgaria, Serbia, Hungary, Slovakia, Austria, Germany). All are interconnected for information exchange.

The connection with the data interface from this equipment is made through serial - USB protocol NMEA 2000.

Digital video recorder (DVR) is a device to which the surveillance cams are connected and which records on a hard digital disk (HDD) images either triggered in motion or continuously. Accessing it via the internet is done via LAN connection.

The ACTISENS DST 2 module is the device to which the depth sensor is connected. Basically, it transmits pulses with a frequency of 200kHz (in the field of ultrasound) to the depth SENSOR (Airmar SS505). The ultrasonic wave generated by the sensor propagates to the bottom of the water. Here the reflection takes place, and the reception of the reflected wave is done by the same sensor. The pulses thus received are sent back to DST 2, and it processes them by transforming them into a digital signal. This signal is further used for PLC processing.

PLC is a digital or analog signal adder and their transformation into digital signals converted into a protocol recognized by its peripherals (ex. 5G router).

The existing CAN-BUS connection to the engine computer (ECM) transmits the data on the engine parameters. The CAN-BUS protocol is based on the engine's dedicated ECM software. Usually, this software and the associated CAN-BUS - USB interface are purchased based on a license from the engine supplier. In our case CATERPILLAR BV.

The demo 5G environment supported by Orange is designed for this use case as it is depicted in Figure 23.

Figure 23: ORO demo environment

The 5G site is installed in Galati port for the two network slices, eMBB and URLLC for the NetApps data services. The 5G E2E communication services are provisioned, and proper resources are configured through the 5G RAN and Core based on the predefined services catalogues. Orange is proposing a list of 5G devices, UEs, CPEs and industrial CPEs to support Galati port use cases, for both NSA and SA 5G technologies and the devices will benefit by 5G Rel. 15/16 for URLLC/eMBB services with 5G RAN support: Samsung S21, Huawei CPE PRO2, Industrial 5G CP Sierra.

The vessels have a series of equipment and installations that provide useful data for safe and efficient navigation. These are a part that provides technical data on the operating parameters of the engines: engine speed, load loading, water temperatures, oil and gas exhaust, fuel consumption etc., and another part provides hydrographic data of the navigable signal. The main sensors and data interfaces will be presented in Figure 24 -Figure 34.

Figure 24: CAT propulsion engine

The connection with the propulsion engines (Figure 24) is made through a CAN-BUS interface (Figure 25) that can be purchased from the equipment supplier, respectively Caterpillar (Diesel Mecanica Constanta).

Figure 25: CAN-BUS connection diagram for CAT propulsion engine

The connection with the depth probe is made by a serial connection type NMEA 0183 or NMEA 2000. Figure 26 shows the connection diagram for the depth sensor. The serial connection is made through the ACTISENSE DST 2 converter (Figure 27) and the depth equipment is Simrad IS20.

Figure 26: Depth sensor connection diagram

Figure 27: Depth-to-serial sensor converter module

The refresh rate for measuring the depth of the Danube water is approximately **1Hz**. The accuracy of the sensor (transducer is Airmar SS 505 type -

Figure 28) is **0.1 m**. Figure 29 shows the sensor on the vessel and Figure 30 illustrates a measurement displayed by the sensor.

Figure 28: Depth sensor type Airmar SS505

Figure 29: Depth sensor on the vessel

Figure 30: Measured Depth.

Navigation information is also obtained from the 2K camera system that is connected to a DVR-NVR (see Figure 31 and Figure 32). Streaming requires **25 Fps**. The DVR is connected to the intranet via a UTP cable to a router. At 8 cameras installed on each ship, the maximum traffic speed could be up to several hundreds of Mbps. As the maximum speed of the ships does not exceed **25 km/h**, the UL/DL bandwidth and service QoS is well supported by the network.

Figure 31: DVR (digital video recorder)

Figure 32: Speed video dome camera

GPS location information is also required for information on the position and speed of the ship. These are taken from the AIS transponder, equipment presents on all ships. The connection with it is made via serial, the same protocol NMEA 200, and baud rate is **34800**. AIS transponder types are SAAB R4 or Periskal PM-1.

Figure 33: 360-degree surveillance video camera

All sensors with serial transmission require a conversion to connect to the router. The signal conversion will be done by PLC equipment (Figure 34), software and protocol will be adequate.

Figure 34: Analog to digital converter type PLC

From here, the connection via mobile communication with the 5G relay is opened, for which Orange Romania is going to provide 5G coverage in a location where there is a sufficiently high traffic of the company's ships.

Data on the water depth, the images in the area where the ship is located and information about the engine parameters must be transmitted to a web server where it can be stored. Also important is the fact that an application must be designed to use this data and retransmit it back to all ships in the group to be used efficiently in the navigation process.

Examples of such applications could be the update on a navigation map from where the navigators can be informed in real time about certain difficult or dangerous navigation areas as seen in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Graphical representation of difficult navigation areas

The data transmitted by the ships will also be useful for dispatchers. The dispatchers are the ones that deal with the monitoring by the human factor of the ship traffic within the company. Water depth data, images of the ship's area and information on engine parameters will be used efficiently and quickly to make decisions about navigating difficult areas. NAVROM has such dispatchers in Galati, Constanta and Turnu Severin. Dispatchers receiving information from ships in bad weather can make quick decisions in difficult navigation situations.

2.2.4.3 Targeted trial scenarios

The trial scenarios can be split in several categories according to the outcome expected:

- collision avoidance
 - using precise positioning sensor and video cameras
- adverse conditions broadcasting and accident prevention in shallow water.
 - using precise positioning sensor and depth sensor
- emergency messages dissemination
 - using engine sensor

For the use case from the Galati port area, our objective is to measure the depths, to take some images between MM 79 and km 155 (see Figure 36).

Figure 36: Digital map of the difficult area

Between Km 152 - 153 there is a portion of the waterway where very shallow depths are recorded, especially in the summer when the Danube water flow is low. Figure 37 illustrates a sand island that sometimes appears above the waterline.

Figure 37: Picture of the difficult area

In principle, the experiment would consist in scanning a ship on which the equipment of this water surface will be installed, recording the measured values of the depths, recording the images captured by the cameras on board the ship and transmitting them via 5G.

The coordinates of the difficult area that will be measured and highlighted are: 45.4253196, 28.0570137, information on the GPS position is taken from the existing AIS TRANSPONDER at the ship (see Figure 38). This data is transmitted via a serial interface to the PLC. Furthermore, measurements will be performed in the area of the Mineralier port and of the Docks Basin.

Figure 38: AIS transponder

This information transmitted in real time will be used to inform the dispatchers (images from at least four 2K cameras) and depths. Also, an application through which establishing certain alert levels can transmit to all ships about the existence of a difficult or dangerous area.

The trial experiment will be supported by a 5G network deployed by Orange in collaboration with the partners in Galati port. The coverage simulation map of the 5G site serving the use case is represented in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Orange 5G site coverage simulation map with the Use case interest area representation

2.3 Use case 3: Automation and Remote Operation of Freight Logistics

2.3.1 Use Case Description

Diakinisis S.A. is a third-party Logistics (3PL) provider with many depots across Greece. The depot that will be used in the framework of the VITAL-5G project incorporates all daily operations met in a typical warehouse,

namely, receiving, put-away to stock, picking (and replenishment of picking from stock locations), checking - final preparation of orders (packaging and labelling), and shipping as well as value-adding services such as co-packing.

This use case intends to demonstrate the feasibility of applying the 5G technology in an overall Logistics context, for optimizing warehousing operations through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) as used by NetApp VS1. This system will make use of the 5G-EVE Athens testbed which will be upgraded to stand-alone and extended at the warehouse premises. The operation of AGVs can be automated and remotely assisted using HD video streaming functionality to enable human interaction (NetApp VS2), while additional AI/ML techniques will be introduced for post-processing operational data in order to improve the end-to-end functionality of the warehouse ecosystem (NetApp VA1). Figure 40 depicts the overall concept of the Athens UC.

Figure 40: Athens use case high-level description

Main issues to be addressed within the use case are the following:

- Lean warehousing: Elimination of time "wastes" in various warehousing operations, such as movements from picking to checking area and put-away operation. The great benefit of AGVs lies in replacing non-value labour and equipment (forklifts) in an operation (NetApp VS1).
- Route optimisation for order picking considering heterogeneous data sources, such as products location, FIFO/FEFO rules, location of employees, final destination of order, product type, sensor data (e.g., humidity, temperature), etc. (NetApps VS1, VA1).
- Availability of remote surveillance and monitoring of processes as well as remote override and handling by human operator. Enabled by multiple UHD streams requiring eMBB slice (NetApps VS1, VS2).
- Advanced AGV operations enabled by 5G connectivity, allowing obstacle / human avoidance, cooperation with human operators ("follow-me function") and collaboration with other automated moving vehicle (URLLC aspects) (NetApps VS1, VS2).
- Storage selection and logistics end-to-end process optimisation through AI and ML techniques allowing for predictive analytics functionality including forecast demand prediction. Based on historic data and all other available data (current orders, holiday traffic, input from sensors and AGV), recommendations for

process changes / upgrades (e.g., truck scheduling, storage volume, personnel needed) will be provided to minimize cost and increase efficiency (NetApps VS1, VA1).

- Intelligent inspection / insurance platform for monitoring and cross-checking of packaged and shipped goods to be used for back-tracking of shipments, cargo insurance, easier customs inspection, etc. (NetApps VA1, VA2).

The use case requires some functionalities that are better provided or only supported by 5G, such as reduced latency, network slicing to support different processes that may present different requirements, and high bit rate to support the use of inputs to the guidance process like high-definition video and/or LIDAR sensors.

The main stakeholders that are involved in UC#3 are:

- Diakinisis, which owns the vertical warehouse facilities and WMS monitoring system data
- OTE, which will provide the 5G connectivity & servers within the warehouse based on 5G testbed
- WINGS, which will provide the AGVs, the NetApps and the platforms to realize most of the functionality
- Incelligent which will provide the NetApps and the functionality to provide the Intelligent inspection / insurance

2.3.2 Related service Key Performance Indicators

The following main Business/services KPIs are targeted in this use case:

- **Productivity increase in picking of order lines per hour by 12.5%**
 - Way of measurement: This KPI (extensively used in warehouses) is used when items (not cartons) are needed to be picked; this is the case in UC#3 as the application area includes pharma products. Measured in lines per shift or per hour. Data collected through the employee scanners used for picking the orders.
 - Baseline: 300 average lines per shift or 40 average lines / hour (currently)
 - Means of achieving KPI: NetApps VS1 will increase the volume of orders executed/h based on the AGVs and it also optimizes the task planning. NetApp VS2 will facilitate the transfer of more cases/h. NetApp VA1 will enable VS1 and VS2.
- **Productivity increase in checking process by 5%**
 - Way of measurement: Measured in units per shift of units per hour. Data collected through scanners used to checking the orders.
 - Baseline: 4.850 units per shift or 650 units per hour
 - Means for achieving KPI: NetApps VS1 will increase the volume of checking orders executed/h based on the AGVs (“follow-me” operation) and it also optimizes the task planning. NetApp VS2 will facilitate the transfer of more units/h to the checking area thus “releasing” personnel which can be assigned other tasks. NetApp VA1 will enable VS1 and VS2.
- **Productivity increase in forklift operation (loading) (20%)**
 - Way of measurement: Measured in units per shift of units per hour.
 - Baseline: 90 pallets per shift or 12 pallets per hour
 - Means for achieving KPI: NetApps VS1 will increase the volume of productivity in terms of pallets loaded based on the AGVs and it also optimizes the task planning. NetApp VS2 will facilitate the transfer of more pallets/h to the picking area; this way personnel will only have to move within the picking area to load the pallets. NetApp VA1 will enable VS1 and VS2.

Additionally, qualitative metrics such as the improvement of health and safety of the supply chain employees will also be assessed.

2.3.3 Use Case 3 NetApps description

Three NetApps will be developed to serve the purpose of the “Automation & remote operation of freight logistics” use case, implemented in the GR facility. Two of those NetApps are vertical agnostic and target the

delivery of generic functionalities that can be reused within the warehouse or any other logistics environment, while the third one will deliver specific vertical functionalities targeting the warehouse environment of GR trial site. The detailed description of the NetApps to be developed as part of this use case are provided below:

2.3.3.1 Vertical Agnostic NetApps

VA1 - Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing:

Data ingestion, consolidation and data processing functionality from distributed data sources; Facilitation of two-way communication and management of on-site equipment; Decision support using offsite analytics; Monitoring of the on-site equipment and NetApp infrastructure. Existing AI / Data analytics tools and inspection application will be used as a starting point, and they will be enhanced with additional pre-processing and analytics functionality, to deliver the envisioned NetApp. A high-level description is provided in the diagram of Figure 41.

VA1's requirements will be fulfilled by software-defined infrastructure organized in logical layers: the NetApp Edge, NetApp Core, NetApp Orchestration and NetApp storage layers.

- *The NetApp Orchestration layer* couples together and synchronizes the whole NetApp infrastructure and services by the means of a common event loop and time scheduling. It also facilitates the monitoring of the NetApp process through metrics collection and watchdogs for each critical component.
- *The NetApp Storage layer provides* persistence and caching services to all other NetApp components. Relational databases, Object and File storage as well as time-series databases will be deployed to support the appropriate data model for different applications. Data caching services will also be provided to support the efficient movement of data through the NetApp services.
- *The NetApp Edge layer* is further divided in the Access, Data Ingestion and Control sub-layers. The Access sub-layer facilitates the efficient and secure communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure through load balancing, name services, authentication, and access control. Raw data from on-site equipment and environmental sensors are collected in real time through the Data Ingestion sub-layer using message queues and REST API endpoints. The Equipment Control sub-layer enables two-way communication by providing feedback to on-site equipment. It also facilitates the management of on-site gateways and IoT devices.
- *The NetApp Core layer* is the main application logic layer which combines data, events, rules, and models in order to provide Decision support. It is further organized in two sub-layers: Data processing and Logic sub-layers. The Data Processing sub-layer reads ingested data from the message queues and REST endpoints and applies transformation operations to convert them in a format appropriate for the logic layer. These transformations include filtering, consolidation, enrichment, aggregation and supplementary operations regarding quality assurance. New functions can be added based on the data needs and the output targets. The Logic sub-layer utilizes the transformed data by feeding the reasoning engines with the appropriate information for decision support. The reasoning engines include a Rule engine, a model-based Inference engine, Forecasting and Field assistance services such as indoor location, routing and navigation. The main goal is the real-time cooperation of hardware and software. Based on the selected algorithms for the above tasks, multiple insights can be derived from the Monitoring Layer like: Analytics and predictions about daily workload, suggestions for daily tasks planning, worker's safety improvement by triggering alarms at dangerous situations, useful reports based on historical and daily data.

Figure 41: VA1 High Level Description

VA1 Inputs:

- On-site equipment sensor data
- Stationary Sensor Data

VA1 Outputs:

- Feedback and management of on-site equipment
- Notifications and warnings
- Historical data for long-term offline analysis and optimisation
- System metrics for monitoring

2.3.3.2 Vertical Specific NetApps

VS1 - Indoor robot navigation & coordination with task planning:

Semi-autonomous decisions/actions taken by the robot including intelligent obstacle avoidance; object recognition and detection; on-the-spot path planning, while intelligent task scheduling based on position, time of day or priority and manual teleoperation via the cloud will also be developed. A high-level description of the VS1 and VS2 is depicted in the diagram of Figure 42.

Figure 42: AGV Functional components for VS1 & VS2

AGVs will be able to detect objects or humans, avoid them and will share a virtual map which is constantly optimized and updated by monitoring the environment in real time. This map will also assist in supervising the AGVs by providing their mark to the staff thus knowing their exact location. All available data will be processed by the AGV controller in real time aiming at the efficient use of drive, steering control and on-the-spot path planning. Using the embedded camera, the AGV will be able to clarify if the detected object is a human and react accordingly by using machine learning. LiDAR sensors provide information about the distance of the objects with high accuracy and in this way a fast reaction time is provided to ensure the avoidance of accidents. Even if the workers will not be in the AGV’s field of vision (e.g., they are behind a wall or a shelf) it will know their exact location using the data from the cameras (and other sensors) that are placed in the warehouse.

For each pallet, the AGV will use the barcode scanner to acquire information regarding the area each of them must be placed. Using the lift controller and the virtual map, the AGV will carry the pallets in a safe way by optimizing the route based on the live data coming from its sensors, considering the people around and any other obstacles. Using data analytics, historical data and real time information the AGV will be able to optimize the storing and picking process. Apart from that, distance calculation can be achieved through the camera and specific distances between pallets can be applied. Space saving in shipping area is crucial as it is smaller in comparison with the other areas. Moreover, remote control of the AGV is also one of the included functionalities. Using the virtual map, workers will be able to set a specific location on the map and the AGV will go there using the optimal route. This functionality will be available through an application running on the workers’ smartphones so that they can monitor and interact with the AGV. The functionalities can be differentiated according to where they are hosted. They will be running either locally on the AGV (based on its sensors) or they will be housed in our cloud/edge platform as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: AGV functionalities and their placement

Running locally on the AGV	Running on the cloud/edge platform
Obstacle Avoidance (LiDAR sensors)	Object recognition (camera images)
On-the-spot path planning	AGV monitoring
	AGV remote control
	Location mapping based on barcodes

VS2 - Human-robot collaboration:

Interaction between robots and human workers in the warehouse; joint task execution i.e., “follow-me” function, item handling, loading, unloading, packaging.

A Human Machine Interface (HMI) will be developed which will allow the workers to set tasks and intervene in the operations of the AGV. Predefined commands such as ‘pick incoming products’, ‘pick checked orders’ or ‘follow me’ will give the worker the opportunity to assign tasks to the AGV. At the ‘follow me’ function the AGV must confirm that the worker has the rights to execute this command. This can be accomplished in two ways: either by using the barcode scanner assuming the worker is wearing a vest containing a barcode on the back that can be scanned or by using the camera and face recognition. The AGV will be following the worker at a predefined distance and each time it will detect the worker’s movements (adjusting its own movements respectively, e.g., stop and wait for loading, continue following the worker, etc.). After the loading procedure is completed, the AGV can be instructed by the worker to transfer the cargo to a designated area in the warehouse.

2.3.4 Site facilities & trial scenarios description

2.3.4.1 Trial facility

Figure 43 Figure 44 present an aerial picture and the top view layout of DIAKINISIS site “Imeros Topos”, respectively, which will be used as the primary demo location of UC#3. In (a) the overall establishment is depicted covering 18.142m² whilst the pharmaceutical part covers 6.824m². The area which is proposed to be utilized for the trials is highlighted in (a) and in (b) where cooling area is also highlighted as this must be excluded. The proposed area covers around 6.000 m2. The following warehouse areas, have been highlighted for use in the demo, as depicted in Figure 44.b, and are defined as follows:

- A. Warehouse Receiving Ramps (incoming pallets)
- B. Designated storage area per customer
- C. Checking station
- D. Shipping station / warehouse Outbound Ramps (outgoing pallets)

Figure 43: DIAKINISIS warehouse at Imeros topos, Athens, Greece

Figure 44: “Imeros Topos” warehouse plans; a) entire facility and b) designated VITAL-5G demo area

2.3.4.2 Trial HW & SW

Regarding the warehouse, the technical details/specifications of the used facilities/equipment are grouped and presented in the following list.

- Storage Capacity
 - Height 11m; total storage area of 18.270m²,
 - Temperature Controlled Areas,
 - Storage Capacity of 21.825 Pallets,
 - Inbound & Outbound through 25 Ramps.
- Safety and Security
 - Alarm and CCTV system,
 - External >2m fence,
 - 24/7 Guard and Additional Patrol during the night,
 - Fire Protection (sprinklers) System according to Greek Fire Standards.
- Power Supply
 - Medium Voltage supply,
 - Oil-filled electrical transformer 800 KVA,
 - Indoor distribution: 5 general low voltage fields and 5 lighting sub-panels.
- Uninterruptible power supply systems
 - Two Power Generating Pairs:
 - DIONYSOS HSW 275E/, 275KVA,
 - GREEN POWER 105KVA.

- Network
 - Wireless MPLS 10 Mbps (Rolaware),
 - backup Wireless MPLS (Wind),
 - Local gateway to Internet 12 Mbps (Rolaware),
 - WiFi corporate,
 - WiFi guest – public Internet (legacy system planned to be upgraded).
- Equipment and Systems
 - RF scanners for picking/packing and forklift operations,
 - Warehouse management system (WMS, provided by Mantis) for supporting warehouse functionality and management,
 - Enterprise Resource Planning system (ERP, provided by SAP) for data collection and message distribution, connected to WMS,
 - Backoffice connected to both ERP and WMS systems,
 - Electrical pallet movers, forklifts,
 - GPS monitoring and sealing shipping containers/trucks.

Regarding the AGV to be used for this UC, we are in search of the most suitable solution. The AGV should fulfil some specific requirements for the purposes of the Use Case 3. The requirements that we have for this AGV are:

- Ability to lift pallets using either a forklift or a lifting AGV
- Ability to access the AGV's software in order to guide it, deploy our functionalities and use it for both automated and human-directed activities.
- Ability to upgrade its connectivity to 5G
- Loading capacity > 50 Kg
- Remote control function
- Ability to be upgraded with Lidar

The embedded equipment is mainly used for the navigation of the AGV and obstacle avoidance. The AGV should be able to move on specific coordinates given by the employees or create its route automated based on the task assigned. Apart from the embedded equipment, the AGV will be also equipped with Lidar, cameras, sensors, barcode scanner and any other auxiliary equipment that could contribute to the expanding of the overall functionalities. Lidar is mainly used for distance calculation between the AGV and obstacles or human on AGV's field of vision. Camera could be useful for both object recognition and monitoring. The barcode scanner will be used to acquire information regarding the exact storage area of each pallet. It will also be used to identify the employees by scanning the barcode on their vests.

We will also equip the warehouse with cameras, localisation devices and IoT sensors in different areas. Cameras will provide us with a better view of the whole facility even when the AGV's camera view range is restricted. Localisation devices will help us monitor the position of both the employees and the AGVs in real time, while IoT sensors will give us some basic metrics of the warehouse such as temperature, humidity etc.

To deploy our analytics and machine learning functionalities we will use servers on-site. These servers will run plenty of different software for image processing (object detection and recognition), forecasting based on historical data, distance calculation, optimum storage location, optimum route for the AGVs and lots of other functionalities that will be deployed through the NetApps. It is vital to use machine learning frameworks to keep our models updated. Some of the basic frameworks to be used are scikit learn, pyTorch and TensorFlow. Using the 5G connectivity, the AGV will have access to the server and will get various information regarding the current state of the warehouse and the pending activities to be made.

2.3.4.3 Targeted trial scenarios

The following scenarios/test cases will be implemented and showcased in the GR Athens UC site:

1. Autonomous transfer of incoming pallets from the input gates (area A in Figure 44) to their respective designated area for storage (area B) via AGV:
 - **Current practice & problem definition.** Each day hundreds of incoming pallets full of products from various customers are delivered via trucks and unloaded to the input gates of the warehouse facility. Each of these pallets is then tagged with a barcode indicating various information about these products including the designated area of storage for this particular pallet. After that, a worker manually goes through every pallet, scans it and picks it up with a manually operated forklift, moving it from the incoming gates area (A) to the storage area (B), that this particular pallet will have to be stores. As the distance between area A and area B is quite large (100 meters on average), and a worker has to go through it every single time for every single pallet, this is a highly time-consuming and labour-intensive process.
 - **VITAL-5G demonstrated scenario.** In order to eliminate this time waste for the workers and to make this process more efficient, during the VITAL-5G trials an AGV equipped with a forklift, lidar, 5G connectivity and a scanner will perform the move of incoming pallets from are A to area B autonomously, without the participation of any worker. The AGV will approach the incoming pallets, one by one and will scan their barcode, acquiring the information about their designated storage point in area B (in collaboration with the warehouse management system). The AGV will then pick up the pallet and will navigate autonomously to area B of the warehouse, avoiding all obstacles and guided with the help of commands from a centralized command server, via 5G connectivity. Once the AGV arrives at the designated area, it will deposit the pallet, and will return to area A to pick up the next one. Different pallets belonging to different customers will be deposited in different points in the storage area B, based on information from the warehouse management system.
2. Autonomous picking and transfer of processed pallets from checking area (area C) to the shipping area (are D) via AGV:
 - **Current practice & problem definition.** After a worker picks an entire pallet of products to be shipped from storage area B, according to a specific outgoing order, they manually take the pallet to the checking area C, where a different employee checks the order, cross-referencing it with online records, to make sure that all products have been picked correctly. Once a pallet has been verified at the checking station it waits at the checking area C, until another worker comes and picks it up with a manually operated forklift and transfers it to the shipping area D of the warehouse, from where it will be loaded onto the trucks. Based on the number of outgoing pallets and the distance between areas C and D (50 meters on average), this is an extremely time-consuming and labour-intensive process which can be avoided.
 - **VITAL-5G demonstrated scenario.** In this scenario demonstrated during the Athens trials, an AGV will replace the workers carrying manually the pallets from the checking area C to the shipping area D, thus saving valuable time and person-months. The AGV will autonomously guide to the checking area and will pick up the first available pallet for shipping. It will then autonomously transfer it to the shipping area D and will deposit it in a designated point, to be later loaded onto the trucks. Once the AGV deposits the pallet, it will autonomously return to the checking area to pick up the next available pallet and bring it to the shipping area.
3. Demonstration of AGV follow-me function (human-robot collaboration) during picking (at area B):
 - **Current practice & problem definition.** In order for a pallet to be shipped from the warehouse to a specific area (e.g., serving all orders in 2-3 neighbouring suburbs of Athens) serving multiple customers, a worker needs to separately pick each and every order and place them on the pallet (before the pallet goes for checking and then shipping). In order to completely full a pallet, a worker needs to go up and down the long storage corridors, picking one order at a time and every time, manually moving the picking pallet with their manual forklift. This is quite an intensive process as a pallet may weight 150-200kg and the worker has to continuously interrupt the picking process to push or pull the pallet back and forth.

- VITAL-5G demonstrated scenario. In the context of the VITAL-5G demonstration, the AGV with the pallet will engage into the “follow-me” function and will follow the picking worker autonomously, saving them the effort and time required for the manual movement of the pallet. As the picking worker moves back and forth the storage corridor picking orders, the AGV will track them and follow them at a close but safe distance, based on onboard sensors and commands from a centralized server via 5G. The worker will be able to place every order they are picking directly onto the pallet of the AGV following them, without worrying about moving the pallet, and may directly continue to picking the next order. Once all the order meant for this pallet are gathered and placed on the AGV by the worker, the AGV will autonomously navigate from area B to the checking area C, where it will deposit the pallet, so the items on it can be checked, before moving them to the shipping area.

Based on the 3 above scenarios, the work carried out and demonstrated within VITAL-5G, will automate significant parts of the end-to-end process within the warehouse, as it covers key activities from incoming products to storage, from storage to picking, from picking to checking and from checking to shipping. During these scenarios complex automation manoeuvres will be demonstrated with the 5G enabled AGVs, including **autonomous mobility** within a complex warehouse environment, **autonomous coordination of the AGV with other another AGV and humans** in the vicinity, to avoid work-place accidents and **remote control of the AGV** by a human operator. These complex AGV functionalities will be enabled through the instantiation of a Cloud/Edge platform communicating with the AGVs, humans and warehouse sensors and cameras, over 5G connectivity, collecting all relevant data and coordinating the AGVs’ movement within the warehouse. As such, ultra-fast and reliable communication among the AGVs, end-devices, sensors/cameras and the platform, becomes critical for the successful operation of AGVs within the warehouse environment.

3 Use Cases Requirements Analysis

In this section, the UCs requirements analysis is presented. Requirements are categorized into three groups: Business, Application and Network requirements.

3.1 Use cases requirements description

3.1.1 Business Requirements

Business requirements have been defined as a result of the workshops organized for each of the UC separately. Different parameters were identified for each vertical trial site which included the key performance indicators related to indoor and inland logistics. Use of 5G technology was considered and decrease in the current cost of logistics operations was considered as a primary requirement. Additionally, to provide efficiency time was also considered as an additional cost.

3.1.2 Application Requirements

Application requirements refer to the definition of the requirements of the Hardware (HW) and Software (SW) that are necessary to be deployed for the realisation of each of the three use cases, as mentioned in Section 2, and that are not part of the network or the vertical facility itself. These are equipment and SW that enable the actual application to perform its core objective (in each case) and usually include⁵:

- End devices such as smartphones, On-Board Units (OBUs), AGVs, AR/VR goggles
- Distributed sensors
- HD cameras
- Application servers (Cloud and/or Edge)

By clearly defining all the devices, servers/platforms and HW/SW requirements of each use case, including their computational and connectivity needs (Throughput/latency per component, reliability, etc.), the design of a proportionate 5G network can be achieved, and the needs of the various UC components can be fully met by the final VITAL-5G platform design. The goal of the application requirements definition is to ensure that the final deployed applications (based on NetApps) will function nominally and without any issues.

All associated information from the trial sites will be sent through 5G vertical to specific applications servers and will be used as input data for the trial specific applications. 5G IoT technology will be used to reduce logistics costs and improve productivity and efficiency to ensure competitiveness with respect to the specific network requirements pertaining to each Use Case.

3.1.3 Network Requirements

The use cases requirements formulated in the project context are related to requirements for 5G Slices. This process is shown as follows in Figure 45. Once the Network slice template is ready, it is instantiated along the different incumbent elements in the network to achieve the required KPIs. The network KPIs are then applied through the 5G network, including 5G UE, 5G radio and 5G core. The overall architecture of 5G network is presented in Figure 46.

⁵ This is not an exhaustive list as different UCs may require the utilization of different components.

Figure 45: GST and NEST in context of the network slice lifecycle

Figure 46: 5G System architecture

The 5G network is composed of several complex and heterogeneous components, blending IT, cloud, and telecommunication technologies. These technologies provide building blocks that can be stacked on top of each other to create the full 5G network, from the foundations up, like the pyramid in Figure 47. At the bottom of the pyramid there are the basic transport technologies, such as front- and backhaul, and the Data Centre network fabric. On those, the NFV infrastructure is built, with cloud technologies such as OpenStack. The Management and Orchestration (MANO) is instead a kernel component for enabling the NFV principles. The telecommunication and service components seen as Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) can be then included in the picture, and with those, at the top of the pyramid, there are the E2E network services. Each level carries along different types of tests that must be performed while deploying and integrating the network, onboarding the VNFs, and providing the services.

Figure 47: The 5G system layers [2]

5G offers network operators the potential to provide new services to new categories of users. The grand objective of 5G is to support three generic services with vastly heterogeneous requirements:

- **Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB):** aims to service more densely populated metropolitan centres with downlink speeds approaching 1 Gbps (gigabits-per-second) indoors, and 300 Mbps (megabits-per-second) outdoors.
- **Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC):** addresses critical communications (safety-critical and mission critical applications) where bandwidth is not quite as important as speed - specifically, an end-to-end (E2E) latency of 1 ms or less.
- **Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC):** 5G enables a 1000X increase of devices connected to the Network, moving from 1K devices per Km² in 4G to 1M devices in 5G. It requires low power consumption and low data rates for very large numbers of connected devices.

Service heterogeneity can be accommodated by network slicing, through which each service is allocated resources to provide performance guarantees and isolation from the other services.

The Network Requirements are the characteristics that the network should offer in order to support the requested applications. The main network requirements that are based on the application requirements are:

Latency: Measures the duration between the transmission of a small data packet from the application layer at the source node and the successful reception at the application layer at the destination node plus the equivalent time needed to carry the response back.

Speed: Speed is set as the minimum data rate required for the user to get a quality experience of the targeted application/use case (it is also the required sustainable data rate).

Reliability: The amount of sent packets successfully delivered to the destination within the time constraint required by the targeted service, divided by the total number of sent packets.

Availability: The network availability is characterized by its availability rate X, defined as follows: the network is available for the targeted communication in X% of the locations where the network is deployed and X% of the time.

Mobility: Mobility refers to the system's ability to provide seamless service experience to users that are moving. In addition to mobile users, the identified 5G use cases show that 5G networks will have to support an increasingly large segment of static and nomadic users/devices.

Broadband connectivity: High data rate provision during high traffic demand periods (It is also a measure of the peak data rate required).

Network Slicing: A network slice, namely “5G slice”, supports the communication service of a particular connection type with a specific way of handling the Control- and User- plane for this service.

Security: Network resilience against signalling-based threads which could cause malicious or unexpected overload. Provision of basic security functions in emergency situations, when part of the infrastructure maybe destroyed or inaccessibly. Protection against malicious attacks that may intend to disrupt the network operation.

Capacity: Capacity is the total amount of traffic exchanged by all devices over the considered area.

Device Density: Up to several hundred thousand simultaneous active connections (means the devices are exchanging data with the network) per square kilometre shall be supported for massive sensor deployments.

The values of the requirements depend on the application that will use the network. For the VITAL-5G Use Cases the values of the network requirements are presented in sub-sections 3.2.3, 3.3.3 and 3.4.3 for UC#1, UC#2 and UC#3 respectively.

3.2 Use case 1: Automated vessel transport

3.2.1 Business Requirements

Based on internal workshops, the business requirements presented in Table 3 were identified:

Table 3: UC#1 Business requirements

UC#1 Business requirements					
No	Requirement	Definition	Unit / type	Min	Max
1	(Improve) Infrastructure Safety (On shore / in waterway)	Current way of measurement is via the online Seafar Portal. All incidents or events are manually or automatically logged on the portal. Specific sheets can be downloaded for an overview over time.	percentage	10%	30%
2	Reduced dwell time in the port area	Inland navigation vessels are currently spending significant time in waiting at terminals for start the loading/unloading operations or when interrupted. This waiting time adds up to the total dwell time. Current way of measurement is via the online Seafar Portal. Navigation time and dwell time are manually or automatically logged on the portal. Specific sheets can be downloaded for an overview.	percentage	20%	40%
3	(Improve) vessel captain and ship planning gaps	The planning operations of inland navigation vessels at terminals inside the port are complex and planners consider a wide set of variables (the dock and lock planning, the schedule of other inland navigation vessels etc.) to complete them. Current way of planning is via the online Seafar Portal. Planning is added on the portal by inland navigation planners and captains	percentage	25%	50%

3.2.2 Application Requirements

Table 4 details the UC#1 application requirements. It puts forward the minimum and maximum of network and end devices parameters that need to be achieved for the success of the Vertical app.

Table 4: UC#1 Application requirements

UC#1 application requirements			
Specific vertical/APP requirements description	Units	Min	Max
Network based requirements			
Number of End Points		1	2
Number (Range) of End Devices per End Point		7	15
Density of End Devices (per sq. meter)	Density per Sq meter	0.5	1.5
Bitrate needs per end point (Mbps)	Mbps	1.5	5
End -to-end Latency (msecs)	msecs	0	100
Highest Acceptable jitter (msec)	msecs		
End Devices			
Type of Device (i.e., Smartphone, TV, VR)		Cameras, VHF transceivers , etc.	
Bitrate required (Mbps)	Mbps	1.5	5
Max Latency Allowable (in msecs)	msecs	0	100
Max Moving Speed (km/h)	km/h	0	50
IPv4 & IPv6 support (or both)		IPv4	
Connection of Device to End Point (Wired/Wireless)		Wired	

The parameters put forward in Table 4 are initially designed for one transport unit, namely one barge. To achieve full remote control of this barge a number of at least six cameras and one "Sensor Processor" (= Linux server) need to be functional. Additional cameras and servers should be possible to be operated at the same specification, as a potential increase in number of cameras might be needed. The number of cameras needed for remote controlling the barges is determined mainly in function of its size, other conditions might also be imposed depending on weather conditions, specific mooring/unmooring operations, type of adjacent traffic on the operation route, etc.

3.2.3 Network Requirements

The expected network KPIs for UC#1 are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: UC#1 Network requirements

UC#1 Network requirements					
No	Requirements	Unit	Y/N	min value	max value
1	Latency (in milliseconds) - Min/MAX	Msec	20	20	40
2	Speed (in Mbps) - Min/MAX - sustained demand	Mbps	150	30	500
3	Reliability (%) - Min/MAX	%	99,99%	99,80%	99.999%
4	Availability (%) - Min/MAX	%	99,99%	99.999%	99.999%
5	Mobility (in m/sec or Km/h) - Min/MAX	Km/h	0-30	0	140
6	Broadband Connectivity (peak demand) - whole train, per each MO (band aggregation oriented)	Y/N or Mbps	N	/	800
7	Network Slicing (Y/N)	Y/N	N		Y
8	Security (Y/N)	Y/N	Y		Y
9	Capacity (Mbps/m ² or Km ²)	Mbps/m ²	0.6	/	1.8
10	Device Density	Dev/Km ²	4	/	300

3.3 Use case 2: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras

3.3.1 Business Requirements

NAVROM is a company fleet in Romania that owns 52 pusher boats of various powers (150 – 3200 HP) and 348 barges of different capacities (1000 – 3200 t) permanently prepared to assure its clients transportation requests on any sector of Danube located between the Black Sea and Regensburg. Within the framework of VITAL-5G project, NAVROM will be the beneficiary of the use case 2 tests. It will have the role of making available some ships, for the installation of equipment with 5G technology, which will be connected to a series of peripherals such as the on-board HD cameras and depth sensors respectively those of the propulsion engines. The UC application will permit a safer port operation and more security regarding navigation of ships with the help of assisted operation / navigation even in severe weather and water conditions.

NAVROM has 200 people as navigating personnel serving the ships. By using the on-board data collection & interfacing for vessels NetApp VS8, the maintenance cost will be reduced due to proper decisions based on on-board diagnosis and monitoring functions and, thus will limit the impact of the human factor to take potentially wrong decisions. Logistics costs may include service, transportation, inventory, and warehouse costs. The partners will measure the logistics costs with and without taking into account OBD-assisted decisions, by comparing the costs reported by the NAVROM port operator for different periods of time, i.e., percentage of

human resources reduction (personnel / crew). The expected target improvement with the exposed solution is the decreasing of the logistic costs with minimum 15%.

The data on the depth of the Danube water and navigable canals are generally useful for the entire inland navigation. They can be inputs for national and international authorities to provide airworthiness data (navigable signal, difficult areas, critical depths, etc.). In this situation could be authorities such as Control Port, Port Captains, and National Administrations of ports and navigable Danube (AFDJ, APDM, ACN). The average number of dangerous events/issues occurred on the Danube River is currently in the order of five events per year. By using the Data stream organisation NetApp VA5, each event will be rapidly, distinctly and granularly classified into dangerous/non-dangerous as well as the type of dangerous event. Warnings will be issued leading to improved reaction time from the vessel crew. To decrease of dangerous navigation events such as vessel collisions, tows striking bridges, ships or barges stuck in the river due to sandbanks or shallow water depth, difficulties, under typical waterway conditions (storms, high water, and flood events), the partners will collect the classified events by the NetApp and measure the decrease against the Romanian database of navigation events. The expected improvement is to decrease with minimum 20% the dangerous navigation events occurring.

Electronic maps used in the navigation process offer currently an accuracy of about 20-35 m (composed of positional accuracy of chartered seabed feature 15-20 m and GNSS accuracy 5- 15m6). The correct safe distance for a ship is made of positional accuracy of chartered seabed feature, half ship's beam, GNSS accuracy, ship orientation and motion. The accuracy of positioning due to GNSS can be improved by the use of distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing NetApp VA1, which will use data from sensors such as velocity, heading, water and wind speed as well as video stream data.

The accuracy of electronic navigation maps indicates vessel course, distance and bearing line from a vessel or in between external objects. The accuracy of positioning due to Geographic Information System (GIS) software is used together with several information layers, e.g., bathymetric maps, map showing recommended routes and showing safe depth limits, obstacles or dangerous places, thus improving the safety navigation.

Fusion of GNSS data with sensor data may lead to a minimum 10% increase in accuracy of electronic navigation maps. Specific requirements related to business/service are provided in Table 6.

Table 6: UC#2 Business requirements

UC#2 Business Requirements					
No.	Business/service requirement description	Units	Applicability	Min	Max
1	Decrease of logistics cost	percentage	200 people as navigating personnel serving the ships	15	50
2	Decrease dangerous navigation events occurrences	percentage	currently in the order of five events per year	20	80
3	Navigation maps accuracy	percentage	currently an accuracy of about 5 - 10 m (composed of positional accuracy of chartered seabed feature 0.3 - 0.5 m and GNSS accuracy 5 - 10m).	10	50
4	Service creation time	min		0	90

3.3.2 Application Requirements

The vertical use case deployment will support a data-enabled assisted navigation application using an IoT sensing system and video cameras installed in Galati port and on a ship and barges. All sensors and cameras will enable the interoperable wireless protocols over a private 5G network and will permit the extension of Internet connectivity of the sensing system. Several sensors such as GPS, humidity, smoke, engine power sensors located in the machine room, will be installed on the ship and barges. These sensors provide relevant information such as velocity, heading, water and wind speed to the ship's local monitoring equipment, allowing the captain and crew to make proper decisions and supporting on-board diagnosis. The crew will also have access to live video streaming from the surroundings through high-definition video cameras in order to achieve high-resolution video streams, high connectivity and low latency addressed by 5G capabilities.

All associated information will be sent through 5G vertical to a central server located in a major port and will be used as input data to update, in real time, an electronic map containing river parameters (water depth, temperature, velocity, different obstacles) and weather conditions. 5G IoT technology will be used to reduce logistics costs and improve productivity and efficiency to ensure competitiveness with respect of the following specific network requirements:

- Number of Endpoints - number of cells deployed for the vertical use case.
- Number of End Devices per 5G cell - number of NAVROM devices attached to the End Point.
- Density of End Devices (per sq. meter) - number of devices deployed in the area.
- Bitrate needs per end points (Mbps) - there is a demand for high-speed values in order to accommodate network and application requirements.
- End to end latency (msecs) - connected devices should be able to communicate without significant delay/ latency less than 20msec. Low Delay/Latency is required between distributed systems / subsystems under test to ensure the integrity and required performance of functional and integration testing. Therefore, maximum delay requirements are posed for the links between the different components, subsystems, and systems under test.
- Highest acceptable jitter (msec) - time-critical communications should be stable and reliable. The maximum timing variation should be less than 20 msec.
- Mobility is a key feature for deploying navigation vertical applications, implying that they can be served by different access networks depending on their location and the availability of each technology. Also, mobility shall be supported seamlessly over various Access Networks.

Specific requirements related to specific Vertical/APP are provided in Table 7.

Table 7: UC#2 Application requirements

UC#2 Application Requirements				
Specific vertical/APP requirements description	Units	Applicability	Min	Max
Network based requirements				
Number of End Points			2	3
Number (Range) of End Devices per End Point			10	30
Density of End Devices (per sq. meter)	Density per m ²		5	10

Bitrate needs per end point (Mbps)	Mbps		20	50
End -to-end Latency (msecs)	msecs		1	5
Highest Acceptable jitter (msec)	msecs		1%	5%
End-devices requirements				
Type of Device (i.e., Smartphone, TV, VR)		smartphone, tablets, PC, DVR	5	10
Bitrate required (Mbps)	Mbps		20	500
Max Latency Allowable (in msecs)	msecs		1	5
Max Moving Speed (km/h)	km/h	NAVROM	1	25
IPv4 & IPv6 support (or both)		both		
Connection of Device to End Point (Wired/Wireless)		wired & wireless	4	10

3.3.3 Network Requirements

One of the main technical network KPIs defined by 5G PPP is the dramatic reduction of the service creation time from the current 90 hours in 4G networks to 90 minutes (or less) in 5G networks. The VITAL-5G portal and Graphical User Interface (GUI) will inherit several key functions from ongoing H2020-ICT-17 project(s) and will thus offer secure, virtualized access, slice provisioning and immediate service creation capabilities to the experimenters.

Most important KPIs for this use case to be used for its validation are listed below:

- Service creation time < 90 min
- Latency for remote steering commands < 20 ms
- Throughput of at least seven full HD video streams for 1 vessel ~ 300 Mbps
- Reliability: 99.99% (less than 52 min. downtime/year) [3]

Specific requirements related to the use case translated into KPIs as latency, throughput, availability, reliability, connectivity, are provided in Table 8, based on the application requirements described in section 3.3.2.

Table 8: UC#2 Network requirements and KPIs

UC#2 Network requirements						
No.	Requirements	Unit	Y/N	min value	max value	KPIs and parameters to be measured
1	Latency (in milliseconds) - Min/MAX	msec		3	20	Latency between terminals and service end points should be less than 20ms

2	Speed (in Mbps) - Min/MAX - sustained demand	Mbps		20	1000	The throughput should be at least 20 Mbps
3	Reliability (%) - Min/MAX	%		99.99%	99.9999%	Reliability > 99.99%
4	Availability (%) - Min/MAX	%		99.99%	99.9999%	Availability > 99.99%
5	Mobility (in m/sec or Km/h) - Min/MAX	Km/h		0	100	
6	Broadband Connectivity (peak UL demand)	Y/N or Mbps	Y		200	
7	Network Slicing (Y/N)	Y/N	Y			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-demand instantiation/deletion/configuration of an E2E network slice and delivery of services over it. QoS guarantees (e.g., latency, bandwidth, etc.) of a slice shall be met.
8	Security (Y/N)	Y/N	Y			
9	Capacity (Mbps/m ² or Km ²)	Mbps/m ²			10	
10	Device Density	Dev/Km2		100	1000	

The main 5G usage scenarios together with the different key capabilities requirements are displayed in Figure 48.

Figure 48: Key capabilities requirements for 5G Usage Scenarios [4]

As shown in Figure 48, eMBB focuses on data rate, network energy efficiency, spectrum efficiency and mobility. On the other hand, URLLC envisages high mobility use cases where the key requirement is the low latency. Finally, the mMTC targets network energy efficiency coupled with high connection density.

The use case we are documenting here requires very high speeds and very low latency involving data enabled assisted navigation and video cameras, and therefore it is a mixture of URLLC and eMBB, ensuring safer port operations and more secure navigation by providing key information (velocity, heading, water and wind speed, live video streaming from the surroundings etc.) to the crew that can thus make proper decisions and support on-board diagnosis.

The use case requirements in terms of network connectivity and network KPIs will be fulfilled by Romanian 5G testbed infrastructure deployed for the use case validation in two main locations, Bucharest for early experiments and NetApps integration and Galati, supporting the demo within the harbour.

3.4 Use case 3: Automation and remote operation of freight logistics

3.4.1 Business Requirements

Based on the analysis of the business needs of DIAKINISIS and the current productivity metrics based on manual labour, the requirements for this use case were defined, along with targeted values of improvement for each of them, based on the VITAL-5G solutions, and they are presented in Table 9.

Table 9: UC#3 Business requirements

UC#3 Business Requirements				
No	Requirement	Definition	Unit / type	Target value
1	Productivity in picking of order lines per hour	Picking of order lines per hour based on AVG operation from receiving to picking area.	order lines / hour	+ 12.5%
2	Productivity in checking process	Final check of completed outgoing packets, ready to be shipped.	shift of units / hour	+ 5%
3	Productivity in forklift operation	Number of pallets transported via forklift, between areas of the warehouse	shift of units / hour	+ 20%
4	Improvement in health and safety for supply chain employees	This is qualitative and side improvement which is expected as a result of usage of AGVs and procedures automation.	N/A	N/A

3.4.2 Application Requirements

Based on the application level needs, the HW and SW requirements were defined, in order to realize this UC according to its full envisioned functionality. The application-level requirements for UC#3 are depicted in Table 10.

Table 10: UC#3 Application requirements

UC#3 Application Requirements			
Attribute	Unit / type	min	max
Network based requirements			
Number of endpoints (Antennas)	-	1	3

Number (Range) of End Devices per End Point	AGVs	1	2
	Smartphones	2	2
	Raspberry Pis	1	2
	Indoor static HD cameras	2	2
Density of End Devices	per sq. meter	1	5
Bitrate needs per end point	Mbps	100/50 (DL/UL)	200/100 (DL/UL)
End -to-end Latency	Msec	10	50
Highest Acceptable jitter	Msec	1	5
Reliability	%	99.99%	99.999%
End-devices requirements			
Type of Devices	AGV, smartphone, IP cameras, Raspberry Pis		
Required Bit-rate	AGV (DL/UL)	5 Mbps / 30 Mbps	
	Smartphone (DL/UL)	10 Mbps / 10 Mbps	
	IP camera (DL/UL)	1 Mbps / 20 Mbps	
	Raspberry Pi (DL/UL)	1 Mbps / 1 Mbps	
Max allowable latency	AGV	20 msec	
	Smartphone	50 msec	
	IP camera	100 msec	
	Raspberry Pi	500 msec	
Max moving speed	AGV	30 km/h	
	Smartphone	10 km/h	
	IP camera	0 km/h	
	Raspberry Pi	0 km/h	
Connection of Device to End Point (Wired/Wireless)	AGV	Wireless	
	Smartphone	Wireless	
	IP camera	Wired	
	Raspberry Pi	Wired	
IPv4 & IPv6 support (or both)	Either is OK		

3.4.3 Network Requirements

The network requirements are presented in Table 11. The values of the requirements were based on the values of the Application requirements that were presented in sub-section 3.4.2.

Table 11: UC#3 Network requirements

UC#3 Network requirements					
No	Requirements	Unit	Y/N	min value	max value
1	Latency (in milliseconds) - Min/MAX	Msec		10	20
2	Speed (in Mbps) - Min/MAX - sustained demand	Mbps		30	90
3	Reliability (%) - Min/MAX	%		99,99900%	99,99990%
4	Availability (%) - Min/MAX	%		99,99900%	99,99990%

5	Mobility (in m/sec or Km/h) - Min/MAX	Km/h		0	130
6	Broadband Connectivity (peak demand) - whole train, per each MO (band aggregation oriented)	Y/N or Mbps	Y		200
7	Network Slicing (Y/N)	Y/N	Y		
8	Security (Y/N)	Y/N	Y		
9	Capacity (Mbps/m ² or Km ²)	Mbps/m ²		0.4	10
10	Device Density	Dev/Km2		100	1000

3.5 General requirements analysis and conclusions

The requirements that were presented and analysed in the previous sub-sections illustrate the targets and the characteristics that the use cases must have. The Business requirements are based on the key performance indicators that are referring on the T&L vertical sector and are identified for each use case. There are 14 requirements in total which target to increase the productivity, the safety and the performance of the tested scenarios and the reduction of the cost and any dangerous unexpected events.

The Application requirements, which are the HW and SW requirements, were the guidance to identify the network requirements. Most of the network parameters take different values for each use case. In Table 12 the values of each requirement are grouped in three ranges, low, medium and high and in Table 13 each use case is displayed in the corresponding value range. Figure 49-Figure 51 show the radar charts that depict the network requirements for UC#1, UC#2 and UC#3 respectively compared to the maximum values that 4G and 5G networks can offer.

VITAL 5G Radar graph for 4G-5G comparison with UC 1 network requirements
Automated Vessel Transoport

Figure 49: UC#1 network requirements radar graph.

VITAL 5G Radar graph for 4G-5G comparison with UC 2 network requirements 5G-connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras

Figure 50: UC#2 network requirements radar graph.

VITAL 5G Radar graph for 4G-5G comparison with UC 3 network requirements Automation and remote operation of freight logistics

Figure 51: UC#3 network requirements radar graph.

Table 12: Network requirements values groups

Network requirements	Low	Medium	High
Fast Response (Latency) (in milliseconds)	≥ 100	$30 \leq \text{fast} < 100$	< 30
Speed (in Mbps)	< 20	$20 \leq \text{medium speed} < 300$	≥ 300
Reliability (%)	99.99%	99.999%	99.99999%
Availability (%)	99.99%	99.999%	99.99999%
Mobility (in Km/h)	$50 \leq$	$50 < \text{medium speed} \leq 200$	$200 < \text{high speed} \leq 500$
Broadband Connectivity (peak demand)	Y/N		
Network Slicing	Y/N		
Security	Y/N		
Capacity (Mbps/m ²)	$100 <$	$100 \leq \text{medium} \leq 1000$	> 1000
Device Density	$100 <$	$100 \leq \text{medium} \leq 1000$	> 1000

Table 13: Use Cases network requirements values

Network requirements	Low	Medium	High
Fast Response (Latency) (in milliseconds)			UC#1, UC#2, UC#3
Speed (in Mbps)		UC#1, UC#3	UC#2
Reliability (%)		UC#1	UC#2, UC#3
Availability (%)		UC#1	UC#2, UC#3
Mobility (in Km/h)	UC#1	UC#1, UC#2, UC#3	
Broadband Connectivity (peak demand)	UC#1, UC#2, UC#3		
Network Slicing	UC#1, UC#2, UC#3		
Security	UC#1, UC#2, UC#3		
Capacity (Mbps/m ²)		UC#2, UC#3	UC#1
Device Density		UC#1, UC#2, UC#3	

From these requirements and use case description the service type could be identified. For UC#1 and UC#2, the service types that should be supported are URLLC and eMBB, while for UC#3 are mMTC, eMBB and URLLC (Table 14).

Table 14: Service Types

Use Case	URLLC	mMTC	eMBB
Use case 1: Automated vessel transport	√		√
Use case 2: 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras	√		√
Use case 3: Automation and remote operation of freight logistics	√	√	√

4 Use Cases utilisation to identify Platform requirements

This section provides an overview of the VITAL-5G platform requirements that have been preliminarily identified through the analysis of the use cases and taking into account the high-level features defined during the proposal phase. These initial requirements will be used as input for Task 1.2 activities, where the functional requirements of the VITAL-5G platform will be further consolidated and extended jointly with the architecture design progress in Task 1.3.

This section initially introduces the high-level VITAL-5G platform architecture (section 4.1), as originally defined at the proposal stage, just to provide a reference for the requirements definition. It should be noted that this architecture was just an initial attempt to identify the major functionalities and building blocks of the VITAL-5G platform, but its specific design will be carried out in Task 1.3 and it may change significantly in terms of internal components and procedures. Section 4.2 provides the list of initial requirements.

4.1 The VITAL-5G platform

The VITAL-5G platform originally defined in the proposal is depicted in Figure 52. The platform provides a unified access point for different stakeholders active in the Transport and Logistic (T&L) area to design, create, deploy, manage and validate T&L NetApps and services for the use cases described in the previous sections, as well as new NetApps developed by 3rd parties external to the VITAL-5G consortium.

Figure 52: VITAL-5G overall concept & envisioned architecture

The open platform consists of an Online Portal which provides the point of access for the entire system through a web-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) that integrates all the tools and functionalities for the deployment, management, monitoring and experimental validation of NetApps in the target 5G facilities. A complementary Open Online Repository allows to store and exchange packages with NetApps and Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) that can be easily combined in end-to-end service chains for added value service compositions. The VITAL-5G platform backend operates on top of distributed 5G facilities, composing the three VITAL-5G testbeds, each of them offering a 5G infrastructure including cloud and edge resources where NetApps can be dynamically instantiated and orchestrated in network slices customized on the basis of the experiment requirements.

4.2 Platform requirements

The VITAL-5G use case descriptions and functional requirements are used to define the platform functionalities to ensure that the open platform will contain all functionalities necessary for NetApp design, on-boarding, deployment, orchestration, monitoring, validation and diagnostics in a trusted and secure service execution environment under realistic conditions. For example, the data enabled assisted navigation system and video cameras used in use case 2 requires a mixture of URLLC and eMBB network slices. Therefore, the open platform must provide the capability of requesting the provisioning or utilisation of network slices compliant with such requirements, giving the possibility of specifying the desired characteristics of the mobile connectivity when declaring and onboarding the associated NetApps. Similarly, the same use case requires the platform to host and execute concurrent services while guaranteeing a certain degree of QoS. This defines the need of creating on demand a number of virtual services composed of one or more NetApps. Such services have to be dynamically deployed over isolated or shared network slices, each of them characterized by a given service profile to be defined through suitable Network Slice Template (NST). The experiment validation implicitly requires mechanisms for KPIs collection, at both the network/infrastructure level and application level, so that they can be processed and validated on the basis of the use case requirements. Most of the platform requirements are actually shared across the three use cases, since all of them require similar procedures for their NetApps design and onboarding and their services' experimental validation. Moreover, also a number of transversal and cross-use case requirements for the platform management and secure access have been identified e.g., to enable different platform access privileges for specific actors, like system administrators, NetApps developers, internal and external experimenters. The resulting initial list of VITAL-5G open platform requirements, identified from the analysis of the three VITAL-5G use cases, along with a brief description, is presented in Table 15.

Table 15: VITAL-5G open platform requirements

ID	Name	Description
1	Web based UI	A graphical user web interface must be provided for all the different actors to access all the functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform. The web-based GUI must provide a graphical, easy to use interface to (i) onboard and visualize NetApps and VNF packages in the online repository and (ii) manage all the procedures related to the experimental validation of T&L services, from their design, up to their creation, configuration, instantiation and Life-Cycle Management (LCM) and, finally, to their monitoring, evaluation and assessment.
2	Multiple users with different profiles organized in groups [RBAC, ABAC]	The VITAL-5G platform should provide identity management access control to protect digital assets and guarantee differentiated access to the different functionalities offered by the platforms. Group classifications can be by role (ex. administrator, user) and by classes (ex. facility, use case). The

		mechanism can either be role-based (RBAC) or attribute-based (ABAC).
3	Host and execute concurrent services and experiment, guaranteeing target QoS	The VITAL-5G platform must be able to deploy, manage and monitor multiple and simultaneous instances of NetApps and services. Each of them can be deployed independently on their target 5G testbed, within isolated or shared network slices, each with guaranteed QoS.
4	Unified NetApp deployment procedures across testbeds	The VITAL-5G platform must expose a common format and methodology to onboard, edit, update, delete, and monitor NetApps and T&L service experiments, independently on the target 5G testbed or its internal technologies or architecture.
5	Centralized license management for NetApps	The VITAL-5G platform should provide mechanisms to verify and manage the licenses associated to the different NetApps, supporting deployment and lifecycle management procedures integrating the validation of such licenses through a centralized and reliable entity. Different types of licences should be supported and modelled in the NetApp package metadata.
6	NetApp and infrastructure metrics monitoring	The VITAL-5G platform should provide visibility into services and NetApps with respect to CPU, memory, and network health metrics, potentially down to the process level.
7	Service & network KPI collection, elaboration, and assessment (infrastructure level KPI assessment)	The VITAL-5G platform must provide mechanisms to measure, collect and evaluate quantifiable KPIs on NetApp service and network utilisation. Such KPIs should be made available through both graphical visualization and analytical values, against which the actor can make fact-based assessments around infrastructure resource performance and demand.
8	NetApps packages onboarding with possibility to declare metadata that helps automated NetApp composition, testing, and validation	When a NetApp is onboarded, the actor must be able to include metadata to facilitate composition, testing, and validation of the NetApp in an automated fashion.
9	NetApps Lifecycle management	The VITAL-5G platform must include mechanisms to enable the onboarding, visualization and removal of NetApp packages and the instantiation, termination and validation of NetApps instances. Further runtime actions may be supported at runtime, including day 2 configuration and scaling.
10	NetApps verification tools	The VITAL-5G platform should implement automated checks for onboarded NetApps to validate their correct deployment and normal behaviour in the target environment.
11	Automated/facilitated NetApp composition for E2E T&L services	The VITAL-5G platform should provide mechanisms to facilitate the composition, testing, and validation of the NetApp, which could be partially or fully automated according to the metadata defined in the NetApp package.

12	OpenAPIs to access VITAL-5G platform functionalities in a programmable manner	In addition to the UI, a subset of the VITAL-5G platform functionalities should be made available for external software components through programmable REST APIs. Such REST APIs should be defined using the OpenAPI specification to simplify the development of external VITAL-5G clients.
13	Slice template onboarding	The VITAL-5G platform should enable the specification of the characteristics of the network slices required for a NetApp. Such characteristics may be defined through a Network Slice Template (NST).
14	Lifecycle management of network slices	The VITAL-5G platform must enable the coordinated management of the network slices required to deploy a NetApp. Such management can be based on the dynamic provisioning, configuration and termination of network slices or rely on the selection of pre-defined and pre-existing network slices at the VITAL-5G testbeds, depending on the specific testbed capabilities. The VITAL-5G platform internal mechanisms to deal with slice management should be fully transparent for the VITAL-5G users.
15	Interaction between the orchestrator and the network and computing infrastructure entities	The VITAL-5G platform must be able to interact with the local NFV MANO and NG-RAN control systems available at the three trial facilities. The details of such interaction must be fully transparent for the VITAL-5G users.
16	AI/ML assisted network slice optimisation and virtual function placement	The VITAL-5G platform should implement internal mechanisms to optimize resource orchestration and virtual function placement e.g., on the basis of the slice type and profile, resource utilisation and service demands. Such mechanisms may be implemented through AI/ML algorithms e.g., for load prediction.
17	Deployment and orchestration of Edge applications	The VITAL-5G platform should have the ability to determine the proper placement of edge applications and to orchestrate edge resources to guarantee the QoS for low-latency services.

5 Conclusions

In this deliverable the high-level Use case description was presented. More specifically, VITAL-5G includes three use cases which focus on the improvement of the Logistics vertical sector and were described in details in order to provide the Key Performance Indicators for each one. Additionally, information about the NetApps that will be deployed and the site facilities where the use cases will be tested, were provided.

The requirements of each use case were also identified and their values were provided. The requirements are separated into three categories: Business requirements, Application requirements and Network requirements. In addition, a comprehensive requirements analysis was presented.

Finally, since these requirements will be used in order to identify the platform requirements in T1.2 (reported in D1.2), the way the requirements will affect on the platform requirements was also presented.

6 References

- [1] Wojke, N., Bewley, A., & Paulus, D. (2017, September). Simple online and realtime tracking with a deep association metric. In 2017 IEEE international conference on image processing (ICIP) (pp. 3645-3649). IEEE.
- [2] 5G-PPP White paper, "Validating 5G Technology Performance Assessing 5G architecture and Application Scenarios "
- [3] Proposal document for "Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities"
- [4] <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/5G>